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SUPSI

University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland
Master of Arts in Interaction Design

Thesis

title

**SLOMO:
Reframing Generative Waste in the creative
process: Towards sustainable educational
frameworks for designing with generative AI**

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This thesis examines the environmental impact of generative AI, focusing on “generative waste”—the discarded content created during iterative image generation, often unnoticed but energy-intensive. By positioning digital consumption as an emerging environmental concern, this research reinterprets sustainable principles—reuse, reduce, recycle, and collect—specifically within the context of design, where generative AI serves as a creative co-creator.

With an emphasis on educational frameworks in visual design, this study seeks to foster digital sustainability among emerging designers and the educational environment. Through slow design principles, the thesis advocates for a mindful and sustainable approach to generative AI, laying a foundation for environmentally conscious design practices and innovative educational strategies in the field.

> THESIS
SLOMO:
REFRAMING GENERATIVE WASTE
IN THE CREATIVE PROCESS

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> DISSERTATION DATE
04 FEBRUARY 2025

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MASTER OF ARTS IN INTERACTION
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A.

RESEARCH

Gen AI
A1.1

“Generative AI is a type of artificial intelligence technology that can produce various types of content, including text, imagery, audio and synthetic data.” (George Lawton, 2023).[2]
 Generative AI (GenAI) has rapidly transformed content creation across multiple mediums. Since the release of models like GPT-3 in 2020, which demonstrated the ability to generate coherent text (Brown et al., 2020)[3], the field has grown at an extraordinary rate. Tools such as ChatGPT, launched in late 2022, quickly gained massive popularity, highlighting the increasing demand for GenAI applications (OpenAI, 2022)[4]. GenAI now extends beyond text, producing high-quality images, audio, and synthetic data through platforms like DALL-E 2 (Ramesh et al., 2022)[5] and Stable Diffusion (Rombach et al., 2022).[6]
 This rapid adoption underscores GenAI’s significant societal impact, blurring the line between human and AI-generated content.

[FIG 1]

Gen AI environmental impact
A1.2

The increasing integration of AI into daily life has sparked concerns over its high energy consumption, particularly in image generation. For example, generating 1,000 images using a model like Stable Diffusion XL can emit as much carbon dioxide as driving a gas-powered car for over four miles (Crownhart, 2024).[7] Additionally, creating just one AI-generated image can consume between 0.01 and 0.29 kilowatt-hours (kWh) of energy, which is roughly equivalent to running a refrigerator for up to 30 minutes (Michael, 2024)[1] or fully charging a smartphone (Heikkilä, 2023)[8]. These examples highlight how energy-intensive AI-generated images can be, putting pressure on power grids and potentially increasing reliance on fossil fuels.

Data centers
A1.3

Beyond AI models, the infrastructure supporting them—particularly data centers—contributes significantly to rising energy consumption. Data centers’ electricity demand is projected to more than double by 2030, potentially reaching 9% of U.S. electricity use (Kindig, 2024)[9]. Globally, electricity consumption from AI, data centers, and cryptocurrencies could hit 800 TWh by 2026, a 75% rise from 2022 levels, with a possible high of 1,050 TWh (IEA). Generative AI systems also require vast amounts of electricity and water for cooling, intensifying environmental concerns and marking the onset of the “internet’s hyper-consumption era” (Rogers, 2024)[10].

[FIG 2]

[FIG 3]

Application of GenAI for design practices

A.1.4

Generative AI has become an essential tool in the design field, revolutionizing the creative process. Since it encompasses the generation of unique works across mediums, from visual content to code. Tools like MidJourney (MidJourney Inc., 2022)[11] and DALL-E (Ramesh et al., 2021)[12] streamline design workflows by automating the generation of visuals based on textual prompts, allowing designers to focus more on creativity (Yannakakis et al., 2014)[13]. These AI models serve as both tools and co-creators, assisting in early ideation and refinement, enhancing both divergent and convergent thinking throughout the design process (Simeone et al., 2022)[14]. In practical applications, AI is integrated into various design processes, from 3D model generation to UI/UX design. Tools such as Autodesk Dreamcatcher (Autodesk Inc., 2017) [15] or Adobe Sensei (Adobe Systems Inc., 2017)[16] offer thousands of variations, optimizing tasks like prototyping and content personalization (Xu, 2023)[17]. However, despite the advantages in productivity, AI tools vary significantly in their energy consumption, with text generation models being less resource-intensive compared to more complex tasks like video and 3D generation, which demand far more energy due to the need for spatial and temporal coherence (Luccioni et al., 2024)[18].

As AI adoption in design increases, balancing the benefits of automation with energy efficiency becomes crucial for sustainable creative practices.

From generation to use:
The content generation gap

A1.5

In 2023, the number of images generated by artificial intelligence surpassed the total amount of photographs produced over 150 years (Redazione Art Vibes, 2023)[19]. By 2024, statistics show that approximately 34 million AI-generated images are created daily. However, only a small fraction of these images is actually utilized or implemented. According to some studies, just 4.8% of the generated images find real application (Lupetti, 2024 - in press).

This raises questions about where the unused content is stored and whether it has any future use. For the purpose of this research, we introduce the term "generative waste" to define the significant portion of images generated by AI tools that often remain within the platform's environment, unused and never downloaded or utilized.

These images likely remain stored on cloud servers or local systems, consuming storage resources and contributing to the environmental impact of AI technologies. At this stage, it is unclear whether this scrap content can be repurposed, as no extensive literature or research has directly addressed the issue. However, the sheer volume of unused content calls for more attention to the management of this digital excess and its potential environmental costs.

[FIG 4]

Number of AI created images
15.470 billion tot.

[FIG 5]

Time it took to reach
15 billion

AI glitches emerging potential

A.1.6

The existing literature doesn't directly address the issue of generative waste but focuses on 'AI errors'—content that fails to meet user expectations. Traditionally seen as flaws to be minimized, recent research highlights the creative potential of these errors. Benjamin et al. (2021)[20] suggest that machine learning uncertainty, a form of computational error, can be used as a design material to open up new possibilities for human-technology interaction. Similarly, da Rocha and Andersen (2020)[21] propose that embracing unintended outcomes and failures in design can reveal new pathways for innovation. In these cases, AI errors transform from technical flaws into generative artifacts, inspiring outcomes that traditional methods might miss.

This literature review investigates the potential of creatively leveraging AI errors, presenting a valuable opportunity to explore how repurposing generated waste content could contribute to reducing energy consumption.

Challenge definition

A.2.1

This project aims to promote a more conscious and responsible use of generative AI during the design process. On one hand, it seeks to raise awareness among users about the environmental impact associated with each content generation and interaction with generative AI, particularly in terms of energy consumption. A key aspect of this challenge is the consideration of AI-generated errors—outputs that deviate from the expected or desired result. Traditionally, these errors are viewed as failures or scrap material, but recent research has begun to explore their creative potential, encouraging designers to embrace these unexpected results as opportunities for innovation rather than discarding them as waste. By rethinking the role of these "errors," designers can experiment with and transform them into valuable design assets, aligning creativity with sustainability. By encouraging designers to reflect on the energy costs of each creative iteration, the project promotes a mindful approach to how AI is used in design. It emphasizes the importance of understanding the unseen environmental footprint tied to generative AI, fostering a shift towards more responsible digital creation.

First HMW

A.3.1

How might we *repurpose* and creatively reuse *discarded* generative AI outputs (generative waste) to both reduce waste and raise *awareness* about the *environmental* impact of the *energy* consumed in their creation ?

Research goals

A.4.1

- > UNDERSTAND GENERATIVE WASTE CONTENT: INVESTIGATE THE NATURE, QUANTITY, AND CHARACTERISTICS OF AI-GENERATED SCRAP CONTENT PRODUCED DURING THE DESIGN PROCESS, FOCUSING ON IMAGES, VIDEOS, AND 3D MODELS.
- > CATEGORIZATION AND CLUSTERING: DEVELOP AN UNDERSTANDING OF HOW DESIGNERS PERCEIVE AND CATEGORIZE THESE DISCARDED OUTPUTS BASED ON POTENTIAL REUSABILITY, AESTHETIC VALUE, OR TECHNICAL QUALITIES.
- > ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT: ASSESS THE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT OF THIS COMPUTATIONAL WASTE PARTICULARLY IN TERMS OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND DIGITAL STORAGE.
- > CREATIVE REUSE: EXPLORE THE POSSIBILITIES FOR REUSING AND REPURPOSING SCRAP CONTENT WITHIN DESIGN WORKFLOWS, POTENTIALLY TURNING DISCARDED OUTPUTS INTO VALUABLE RESOURCES.

Target groups

A.4.2

PRIMARY GROUPS:

1. DESIGN PRACTITIONERS USING GENERATIVE AI TOOLS
2. DESIGN EDUCATORS
3. DESIGN STUDENTS

SECONDARY GROUPS:

1. AI RESEARCHERS INTERESTED IN THE SUSTAINABILITY OF DIGITAL PRACTICES.

Research methods

A.4.3

- > LITERATURE REVIEW: ANALYZE EXISTING STUDIES ON AI-GENERATED CONTENT, DIGITAL WASTE, AND SUSTAINABLE DESIGN PRACTICES TO CONTEXTUALIZE COMPUTATIONAL WASTE CONTENT WITHIN BROADER ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERNS.
- > DATA COLLECTION OF COMPUTATIONAL WASTE: CREATE A DATABASE OF UNUSED AI-GENERATED IMAGES, VIDEOS, AND 3D MODELS COLLECTED FROM VARIOUS DESIGN PROJECTS, DOCUMENTING DETAILS SUCH AS PROMPT ITERATIONS, FILE TYPES, AND ENERGY USAGE ESTIMATES.
- > CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP: ORGANIZE A COLLABORATIVE WORKSHOP WITH DESIGNERS TO REVIEW AND CATEGORIZE THE SCRAP CONTENT, HELPING TO UNDERSTAND THEIR THOUGHT PROCESS WHEN DETERMINING POTENTIAL REUSE. DESIGNERS WILL BE ASKED TO TAG AND CLUSTER CONTENT BASED ON AESTHETIC, FUNCTIONAL, OR CREATIVE CRITERIA.
- > SURVEYS AND INTERVIEWS:
 - SURVEYS: DISTRIBUTE SURVEYS TO DESIGNERS TO GATHER INSIGHTS ON THEIR AWARENESS OF SCRAP CONTENT AND ITS POTENTIAL REUSE.
 - INTERVIEWS: CONDUCT SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS WITH DESIGNERS AND ENVIRONMENTAL EXPERTS TO EXPLORE THEIR VIEWS ON THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AI-GENERATED OUTPUTS AND HOW SCRAP CONTENT MIGHT FIT INTO FUTURE WORKFLOWS.

Research outcomes

A.4.4

- > QUANTITATIVE DATA:
BUILD A DATASET OF AI-GENERATED SCRAP CONTENT, CONSISTING OF AT LEAST 200 ITEMS (IMAGES, VIDEOS, 3D MODELS).
COLLECT RESPONSES FROM AT LEAST 20 DESIGNERS THROUGH SURVEYS REGARDING THEIR EXPERIENCE WITH GENERATIVE AI AND SCRAP CONTENT.
- > QUALITATIVE DATA:
ORGANIZE 1 CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP WITH 10 DESIGNERS, FOCUSING ON CATEGORIZATION AND REUSE STRATEGIES FOR SCRAP CONTENT.
CONDUCT AT LEAST 2 INTERVIEWS WITH EXPERTS IN DESIGN AND GENAI SUSTAINABILITY TO EXPLORE INSIGHTS INTO HOW SCRAP CONTENT COULD BE REPURPOSED.
- > DELIVERABLES:
A REPORT OUTLINING THE PATTERNS IDENTIFIED IN THE CATEGORIZATION OF COMPUTATIONAL WASTE.
PROPOSALS FOR POTENTIAL REUSE STRATEGIES, INCLUDING WORKFLOW ADJUSTMENTS FOR INTEGRATING COMPUTATIONAL WASTE.
ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS DOCUMENTING THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND POTENTIAL BENEFITS ASSOCIATED WITH REUSING SCRAP CONTENT.

Timeline

A.4.5

- WEEK 1 (12-19/09):
 - > PRIMARY RESEARCH AND IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE
 - > DATABASE CONTENT COLLECTION
 - > SURVEY DISTRIBUTION
 - > CO-WORKSHOP DEFINITION & ORGANIZATION (ON-LINE AND IN PRESENCE)
- WEEK 2 (20-27/09):
 - > INTERVIEWS
 - > SURVEY DATA COLLECTION & INSIGHT DEFINITION
 - > DATABASE CONTENT COLLECTION
 - > CO-WORKSHOP ORGANIZATION (ON-LINE AND IN PRESENCE)
- WEEK 3 (28-04/10):
 - > DATABASE CONTENT COLLECTION
 - > CO-WORKSHOP WITH DESIGNERS
- WEEK 4 (05-12/10):
 - > CO-WORKSHOP INSIGHT AND DATA SUMMARY
 - > DATABASE CONTENT COLLECTION
- WEEK 5 (13-15/10):
 - > DELIVERABLES REFINEMENT

Evaluation Metrics

A.4.6

- > ENGAGEMENT WITH GENERATIVE WASTE:
MEASURE THE ENGAGEMENT OF WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS WITH THE PROVIDED SCRAP CONTENT, ASSESSING HOW THEY CATEGORIZE AND SUGGEST POTENTIAL REUSE.
- > ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ANALYSIS:
QUANTIFY THE ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS OF REUSING COMPUTATIONAL WASTE, FOCUSING ON ENERGY SAVINGS COMPARED TO GENERATING NEW AI OUTPUTS.
- > DESIGNER FEEDBACK:
EVALUATE DESIGNER FEEDBACK ON THE FEASIBILITY OF INCORPORATING COMPUTATIONAL WASTE INTO THEIR WORKFLOWS, BOTH IN TERMS OF CREATIVITY AND EFFICIENCY.

Methodology

A.5.1

The methodology used for the development of this research paper is structured in an approach aimed at ensuring a systematic collection and processing of information. The methodological process relies on thorough desk research, integrated with external contributions for each macro-topic addressed. Specifically, these contributions include:

- > **Literature review and desk research:** developed in order to gather the state of the art for both, Generative AI (GenAI) consumption and Generative AI applied within the design field.
- > **Interviews:** conducted with experts and professionals to gather qualified insights and enrich the analysis with direct experiences.
- > **Questionnaires:** administered to a representative sample with the aim of collecting quantitative and qualitative data, offering a broader and more contextualized perspective on the topics addressed, and allowing the project to focus on user needs.
- > **Collection of qualitative data:** including images and content derived from generative processes, in order to evaluate how these materials can be reused and categorized.
- > **Co-annotation and co-creation workshop:** organized to explore in a practical way the value of the collected content and to carry out its categorization.

This data collection process, along with its incorporation into the thesis, aims to simplify the complexity of the narrative and facilitate the understanding of the analyzed process, allowing for a thorough exploration of the entire path that led to the project's verticalization and enabling solid and well-founded conclusions to be drawn.

[FIG 6]

Mapping GenAI
consumption

A.5.2

Generative AI represents an environmental problem that is unfortunately still not extensively and thoroughly understood. The ability to accurately map the environmental impact of artificial intelligence remains difficult to implement and to obtain since it involves not only energy consumption, but many other factors.

To position the project and define its objectives, it is necessary to thoroughly understand what the consumption of generative AI is and where the project can effectively operate and make a positive contribution.

Starting from the development of a generative artificial intelligence model, the initial point of reference is the mineral resources needed for hardware production. The creation of advanced electronic devices requires the use of rare earth elements and other critical minerals such as lithium, cobalt, and neodymium.

These materials are essential for the production of key components such as high-performance processors, memories, and batteries used in data centers.

The extraction and processing of these resources result in significant environmental impacts, including ecosystem degradation, soil and water pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, mining practices in certain regions can be associated with unsafe working conditions and human rights violations. Therefore, it is crucial to understand not only the energy consumption during the operation of AI models but also the ecological footprint associated with the entire lifecycle of the hardware devices needed for their development and functioning. (SCISPACE, n.d.)[22]

The article "Anatomy of an AI System" highlights how the complexity and impact of these systems go far beyond mere energy consumption or the use of rare materials.

The article emphasizes the interconnection between resource extraction, industrial production, global logistics, human labor, and electronic waste management. Every stage of the lifecycle of a generative AI system contributes to its overall ecological and social footprint. For instance, the production of a single device involves the extraction of materials from various parts of the world, often in degraded environmental conditions and with unethical labor practices. Manufacturing requires energy-intensive processes and can result in harmful emissions. Additionally, the operation of AI models necessitates infrastructure such as data centers, which consume enormous amounts of energy and water resources for cooling.

The aspect of end-of-life disposal for these devices, which generates electronic waste that is difficult to recycle

and potentially harmful to the environment, should not be overlooked. On a social level, generative AI can involve the use of underpaid labor for activities such as data labeling or content moderation, often in contexts with poor labor protections. Moreover, the concentration of technological control in a few large companies can create power imbalances and influence global socio-economic dynamics. (Crawford and Joler, 2018) [23]

[FIG 7]

Expertise interviews

A.5.3

To gain a deeper understanding of the environmental impact related to artificial intelligence models, two experts were interviewed. Their insights provided valuable perspectives and helped to enrich the research by offering a more comprehensive view of the issue. The interviews allowed for an exploration of the complexities and nuances associated with AI-related pollution, which are often overlooked in standard analyses. By integrating expert opinions, the research aims to present a more accurate and detailed account of the challenges and potential solutions surrounding the environmental footprint of generative AI.

JOSÉ HALLOY

JOSÉ HALLOY, A PHYSICIST AND CO-FOUNDER OF THE LABORATOIRE INTERDISCIPLINAIRE DES ÉNERGIES DE DEMAIN (LIED CNRS UMR8236), HAS BEEN CONDUCTING INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH SINCE 2011. HIS WORK, FRAMED WITHIN AN “EARTH SYSTEM” PERSPECTIVE, AIMS TO DEVELOP A SYSTEMIC UNDERSTANDING OF SUSTAINABILITY BY INCORPORATING SOCIAL SCIENCES AND ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES.

KEY FINDINGS

ENHANCING ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENTS CAN UNINTENTIONALLY LEAD TO HIGHER TOTAL ENERGY AND MATERIAL CONSUMPTION DUE TO THE REBOUND EFFECT. AS DEVICES BECOME MORE EFFICIENT, POWERFUL, AND AFFORDABLE, THEY ARE USED MORE EXTENSIVELY AND REPLACED MORE FREQUENTLY, INCREASING OVERALL RESOURCE USE, ENERGY CONSUMPTION, AND ELECTRONIC WASTE. TO MITIGATE THIS REBOUND EFFECT, IT'S CRUCIAL TO FOCUS ON REDUCING THE ABSOLUTE AMOUNTS OF ENERGY AND MATERIALS CONSUMED, NOT JUST ON IMPROVING EFFICIENCY.

> THE MOST PRESSING SUSTAINABILITY ISSUE IN DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IS ESCALATING MATERIAL CONSUMPTION AND ELECTRONIC WASTE (E-WASTE) RATHER THAN ENERGY USAGE ALONE. THIS ELECTRONIC OVERPRODUCTION CAN LEAD TO SHORTAGES OF MATERIALS IN THE NEAR FUTURE. TO ACHIEVE TRUE SUSTAINABILITY IN THE DIGITAL INDUSTRY, WE MUST PRIORITIZE EXTENDING THE LIFESPAN OF ELECTRONIC DEVICES THROUGH REUSE, REPAIR, AND REFURBISHMENT.

> THE EXPONENTIAL INCREASE IN DIGITAL DATA PRODUCTION LEADS TO GREATER DEMANDS FOR STORAGE AND PROCESSING POWER, REQUIRING MORE DEVICES AND EXPANSIVE DATA CENTERS. THIS NOT ONLY ESCALATES ENERGY CONSUMPTION BUT ALSO CONTRIBUTES TO ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION DUE TO THE PRODUCTION AND DISPOSAL OF HARDWARE. TO PROMOTE SUSTAINABILITY, IT IS ESSENTIAL TO LIMIT THE GENERATION OF EXCESSIVE DATA—MAINTAINING A CONSTANT VOLUME OF BITS.

> PRACTICES SUCH AS STORING AND SHARING EXTENSIVE DATASETS TO AVOID RERUNNING COMPLEX MODELS—COMMON IN FIELDS LIKE CLIMATOLOGY—PROMOTE THE REUSE AND EXCHANGE OF EXISTING DATA.

KEY INSIGHTS

THE INSIGHTS FROM JOSÉ HALLOY'S INTERVIEW REVEAL CRITICAL STRATEGIES FOR ACHIEVING SUSTAINABILITY IN THE DIGITAL INDUSTRY. THE PRIMARY EMPHASIS LIES IN MOVING BEYOND IMPROVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND ADDRESSING THE CORE ISSUE OF ESCALATING RESOURCE CONSUMPTION DRIVEN BY EXCESSIVE DATA PRODUCTION. THE KEY TAKEAWAYS TO ADDRESS BETTER THE PROBLEM OF “GENERATIVE WASTE” ARE:

> LIMIT THE GENERATION OF NEW DATA: THE EXPONENTIAL GROWTH OF DIGITAL DATA LEADS TO GREATER ENERGY AND RESOURCE CONSUMPTION DUE TO THE NEED FOR MORE DEVICES AND LARGER DATA CENTERS. REDUCING THE CREATION OF EXCESSIVE CONTENT IS CRUCIAL TO MITIGATE THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.

> PROMOTE THE REUSE AND SHARING OF EXISTING DATA: ENCOURAGING THE REUSE AND EXCHANGE OF ALREADY AVAILABLE DATASETS, CAN SIGNIFICANTLY REDUCE THE NEED FOR NEW DATA GENERATION AND ADDITIONAL COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES. THIS STRATEGY HELPS LOWER ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND MINIMIZES THE ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION ASSOCIATED WITH HARDWARE PRODUCTION AND DISPOSAL.

FRÉDÉRIQUE KRUPA

FRÉDÉRIQUE KRUPA, PH.D., IS THE DIRECTOR OF THE HUMAN MACHINE DESIGN LAB AT THE ECOLE DE DESIGN NANTES ATLANTIQUE, LEADING RESEARCH IN UX/UI AND AI. SHE PREVIOUSLY FOUNDED AND CHAIRED THE TRANSDISCIPLINARY NEW MEDIA AND COMMUNICATION DESIGN PROGRAM AT PARIS COLLEGE OF ART AND CO-FOUNDED THE SOFTWARE FIRM SIMPLE IS BEAUTIFUL. KRUPA HAS TAUGHT AT PARSONS SCHOOL OF DESIGN, RISD, UNIVERSITY OF THE ARTS, AND ENSAD, AND HER CURRENT RESEARCH FOCUSES ON AI/MACHINE LEARNING ETHICS.

KEY FINDINGS

THE RAPID GROWTH OF LARGE AI MODELS, SUCH AS LANGUAGE MODELS, IS RESULTING IN UNSUSTAINABLE LEVELS OF ENERGY AND RESOURCE CONSUMPTION. DATA CENTERS THAT SUPPORT THESE MODELS CONSUME VAST AMOUNTS OF ENERGY—OFTEN EXCEEDING THAT OF ENTIRE NATIONS—PUTTING IMMENSE PRESSURE ON INFRASTRUCTURE AND DAMAGING THE ENVIRONMENT. TO ADDRESS THESE ISSUES, IT'S ESSENTIAL TO MANAGE AND REDUCE AI'S ENERGY USAGE, RETHINK THE SCALE OF MODEL DEVELOPMENT, AND FIND MORE ENVIRONMENTALLY CONSCIOUS WAYS TO OPERATE THESE DATA CENTERS.

> RESOURCE-INTENSIVE NATURE OF AI DEVELOPMENT: BUILDING NEURAL NETWORKS DEMANDS A HIGH LEVEL OF COMPUTATIONAL POWER AND HUMAN LABOR. THE PROCESS REQUIRES EXTENSIVE DATA CURATION, TIME-INTENSIVE MODEL TRAINING, AND COMPLEX DEPLOYMENT, MAKING AI DEVELOPMENT BOTH RESOURCE- AND ENERGY-INTENSIVE.

> DATA PRIVACY AND OWNERSHIP CONCERNS: USERS OF GENERATIVE AI PLATFORMS LIKE MIDJOURNEY OFTEN UNKNOWINGLY GIVE UP PRIVACY AND OWNERSHIP RIGHTS OVER THEIR DATA AND GENERATED CONTENT. COMPANIES MAY COLLECT AND UTILIZE ALL USER INTERACTIONS FOR THEIR OWN BENEFIT, RAISING SERIOUS CONCERNS ABOUT DATA PRIVACY AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY. IT IS CRUCIAL FOR USERS TO REVIEW TERMS OF SERVICE CAREFULLY AND UNDERSTAND HOW THEIR DATA MAY BE USED.

> VALUE OF ANOMALIES IN AI OUTPUTS: ANALYZING GLITCHES AND ANOMALIES IN AI OUTPUTS CAN SOMETIMES YIELD MORE MEANINGFUL INSIGHTS THAN FOCUSING SOLELY ON SUCCESSFUL RESULTS. THESE UNEXPECTED OUTCOMES PROVIDE A WINDOW INTO THE INNER WORKINGS OF AI SYSTEMS AND REVEAL POTENTIAL AREAS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT.

KEY INSIGHTS

THE INSIGHTS FROM FRÉDÉRIQUE KRUPA EMPHASIZE THE COMPLEXITIES OF ACHIEVING SUSTAINABILITY IN GENERATIVE AI DEVELOPMENT. EVEN EFFORTS AIMED AT SUPPORTING SUSTAINABILITY CAN BECOME RESOURCE-INTENSIVE, AS THE "GENERATIVE WASTE" PRODUCED—SUCH AS DISCARDED OUTPUTS AND ERRORS—STILL CONSUMES STORAGE SPACE AND CONTRIBUTES TO DATA CENTER OVERUSE. A MORE MINDFUL APPROACH IS NEEDED TO REPURPOSE THESE UNCONVENTIONAL OUTPUTS. FURTHERMORE, BASED ON HER WORK WITH GENERATIVE AI BIASES, KRUPA SUGGESTS THAT UNEXPECTED AND IMPERFECT OUTPUTS OFTEN PROVIDE MORE VALUE AND INSIGHTS THAN SUCCESSFUL RESULTS. THE KEY TAKEAWAYS TO ADDRESS BETTER THE PROBLEM OF "GENERATIVE WASTE" ARE:

> IMPLEMENT STRATEGIES TO REDUCE GENERATIVE WASTE: FOCUS ON MINIMIZING THE PRODUCTION OF UNNECESSARY AI OUTPUTS AND MANAGING DATA STORAGE MORE EFFECTIVELY. IMPLEMENTING DATA OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES AND REDUCING REDUNDANT CONTENT GENERATION CAN HELP DECREASE THE BURDEN ON DATA CENTERS.

> ENCOURAGE EXPLORATION OF IMPERFECT AI OUTPUTS: IMPERFECT OR UNEXPECTED OUTPUTS OFTEN OFFER DEEPER INSIGHTS INTO THE WORKINGS OF AI SYSTEMS. LEVERAGING THESE ANOMA-

LIES CAN LEAD TO NEW RESEARCH DIRECTIONS AND INNOVATIVE APPLICATIONS, TURNING POTENTIAL WASTE INTO VALUABLE RESOURCES FOR DISCOVERY AND EXPERIMENTATION.

Interviews results

A.5.4

The findings from the interviews have prompted a critical reflection on the wide-ranging environmental consequences associated with the creation and use of AI models. While completely eliminating the environmental impact of AI remains a challenging goal, a strategic approach can help mitigate these effects and foster more sustainable practices. Both experts emphasize the need to reduce excessive content generation, promote the reuse of existing data, and rethink our use of digital resources. By prioritizing these actions, the project can contribute to a more responsible use of technology, reducing its ecological footprint and promoting a mindful approach to content creation and data management. The focus should be on practical strategies that encourage efficiency, reuse, and innovative repurposing of AI outputs, thereby paving the way for a more sustainable and conscientious digital future.

Generative waste
positioning

A.5.5

The issue of “generative waste,” as highlighted in the map (page 32), primarily emerges during the user interaction phase with AI models. This phase is characterized by a substantial use of resources due to the continuous feeding of the models, frequent updates to enhance performance, and the massive production of data (bits). The data generated and accumulated during usage requires extensive infrastructure for storage on servers, which in turn leads to increased energy consumption and resource depletion.

The concept of generative waste can be further categorized within a broader framework: digital waste. Digital waste refers to any stored data that no longer serves a meaningful purpose. This can include everything from unused internet downloads and forgotten photos to archived emails, outdated marketing materials, and obsolete spreadsheets. By placing generative waste within the larger context of digital waste, it becomes clear that the environmental impact of unused and redundant data extends far beyond AI outputs, highlighting the need for a more mindful and efficient management of all digital content. (Levis.R, 2024, May 1)[24]

[FIG 8]

[FIG 9]

Case studies

A.5.6

Given the lack of literature and dedicated projects specifically addressing generative waste, the following case studies are presented to explore various interpretations that prioritize sustainability and digital waste management. This topic, like generative waste, remains underexplored and not widely discussed, highlighting the need for a deeper investigation into its impact and potential solutions.

DIGITAL WASTE PROJECT

THE “ECO-DIGITAL LITERACY AND CITIZENSHIP FOR OUR PLANET AND FUTURE” (DIGITAL WASTE) PROJECT IS A STRATEGIC INITIATIVE AIMED AT ADDRESSING THE GROWING ISSUE OF DIGITAL WASTE WHILE PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES THROUGH INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION. THE PROJECT SERVES AS BOTH AN EDUCATIONAL PLATFORM AND AN ADVOCACY CAMPAIGN TO RAISE AWARENESS ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DIGITAL WASTE AND EMPOWER YOUNG PEOPLE TO TAKE ACTION.

PURPOSE:

THE PRIMARY PURPOSE OF THE PROJECT IS TO TACKLE THE ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIETAL CHALLENGES POSED BY DIGITAL WASTE—SUCH AS EXCESSIVE DATA STORAGE AND THE RELATED INCREASE IN ENERGY CONSUMPTION—BY ENHANCING DIGITAL LITERACY AND PROMOTING ECOLOGICAL RESPONSIBILITY. THE INITIATIVE TARGETS YOUNG PEOPLE, AIMING TO TRANSFORM THEM INTO ACTIVE, INFORMED CITIZENS WHO UNDERSTAND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIGITAL BEHAVIORS AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY.

MOBILE APPLICATION ANALYSIS:

THE DIGITAL WASTE MOBILE APPLICATION IS ONE OF THE KEY TOOLS DEVELOPED WITHIN THE PROJECT TO SUPPORT ITS OBJECTIVES. THIS APP OFFERS A PRACTICAL SOLUTION FOR MANAGING DIGITAL WASTE ON PERSONAL DEVICES, DIRECTLY LINKING USER ACTIONS TO ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS.

FUNCTIONALITIES:

DATA CLEANUP: THE APP IDENTIFIES AND CATEGORIZES UNNECESSARY FILES, SUCH AS JUNK FILES, DUPLICATE PHOTOS, UNUSED VIDEOS, OUTDATED DOCUMENTS, AND AUDIO FILES THAT CONTRIBUTE TO DATA CLUTTER AND INCREASED STORAGE REQUIREMENTS.
EFFICIENT DELETION: USERS CAN EASILY DELETE SELECTED FILES, THEREBY FREEING UP STORAGE SPACE AND OPTIMIZING DEVICE PERFORMANCE.
CARBON FOOTPRINT CALCULATION: A UNIQUE FEATURE OF THE APP IS ITS ABILITY TO CALCULATE THE CARBON EMISSIONS SAVED THROUGH FILE DELETION, HELPING USERS UNDERSTAND THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF THEIR ACTIONS AND PROMOTING MORE SUSTAINABLE DIGITAL HABITS.
EDUCATIONAL COMPONENT: THE APP PROVIDES INSIGHTS AND TIPS ON HOW TO REDUCE DIGITAL WASTE AND ENCOURAGES USERS TO ADOPT ECO-FRIENDLY DIGITAL PRACTICES.

ECOLOGIA DIGITALE

THE BOOK “ECOLOGIA DIGITALE”, AUTHORED BY A DIVERSE GROUP OF EXPERTS, EXPLORES THE ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL, AND ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND AIMS TO PROMOTE A MORE SUSTAINABLE AND CONSCIOUS APPROACH TO DIGITAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT. THIS COMPREHENSIVE STUDY HIGHLIGHTS THE OFTEN OVERLOOKED ECOLOGICAL FOOTPRINT OF OUR DIGITAL HABITS AND PROPOSES STRATEGIES FOR MITIGATING THEIR NEGATIVE IMPACTS.

PURPOSE:

THE PRIMARY AIM OF THE BOOK IS TO RAISE AWARENESS ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT OF DIGITAL ACTIVITIES AND PROMOTE A SHIFT TOWARDS MORE SUSTAINABLE AND RESPONSIBLE DIGITAL PRACTICES. IT NOT ONLY HIGHLIGHTS THE NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES OF THE CURRENT DIGITAL PARADIGM BUT ALSO PRESENTS ACTIONABLE SOLUTIONS TO REDUCE DIGITAL WASTE AND ITS ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT.

OBJECTIVES:

ANALYZE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT: THE BOOK THOROUGHLY EXAMINES HOW EVERYDAY DIGITAL ACTIVITIES, SUCH AS SENDING EMAILS, WATCHING VIDEOS, OR STORING FILES, CONTRIBUTE TO ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND CARBON EMISSIONS. IT EMPHASIZES THE ROLE OF DATA CENTERS—THE PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SUPPORTING CLOUD COMPUTING AND DATA STORAGE—AS SIGNIFICANT SOURCES OF GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS.

EXPLORE SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES: ECOLOGIA DIGITALE ALSO ADDRESSES THE SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS OF BIG TECH’S CONTROL OVER DIGITAL RESOURCES, FOCUSING ON ISSUES SUCH AS DATA PRIVACY, EXPLOITATION, AND THE COMMODIFICATION OF USER ATTENTION. THE AUTHORS ARGUE THAT THE UNCHECKED GROWTH AND DOMINANCE OF THESE COMPANIES PERPETUATE AN UNSUSTAINABLE CYCLE OF OVERPRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION.

PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE DIGITAL PRACTICES: THE BOOK ADVOCATES FOR A MORE CONSCIOUS APPROACH TO DIGITAL CONSUMPTION, ENCOURAGING INDIVIDUALS AND ORGANIZATIONS TO ADOPT PRACTICES THAT MINIMIZE DIGITAL WASTE AND ENERGY USE. IT SUGGESTS A SHIFT IN MINDSET WHERE DIGITAL RESOURCES ARE SEEN AS FINITE AND VALUABLE, REQUIRING CAREFUL MANAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABLE UTILIZATION.

AUTORS:

GERRY MCGOVERN, CARLO GUBITOSA, FRANCESCO CARA, GIUSEPPE PALAZZO, ALBERTO PRINA CERAI, ALESSANDRO CILLARIO, STEFANO ONOFRI, GIACOMO VENEZIA, STEFANA BROADBENT, DARIO PIZZULI, STEFANO TRUMPY, TOMMASO GOISIS, STEFANIA PAOLAZZI, MAURIZIO NAPOLITANO, GIULIA MONTELEONE, MATTEO SPINI, NICOLA BONOTTO, SAVINO CURCI, ANTONIO ALESSIO DI PINTO, GAUTHIER ROUSSILHE, MASSIMO ACANFORA, DUCCIO FACCHINI, ANDREA SICCARDO, MARIANNA USUELLI, STEFANO ZOJA.

CARBON CALCULATOR

THE WEBSITE CARBON CALCULATOR IS AN ONLINE PLATFORM DEDICATED TO RAISING AWARENESS ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF WEBSITES AND PROMOTING DIGITAL SUSTAINABILITY. BY PROVIDING A TOOL TO CALCULATE THE CARBON EMISSIONS GENERATED DURING THE LOADING AND BROWSING OF A WEBPAGE, THE PLATFORM AIMS TO ENCOURAGE WEBSITE OWNERS, DEVELOPERS, AND BUSINESSES TO OPTIMIZE THEIR SITES FOR GREATER ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND REDUCED CARBON FOOTPRINT.

PURPOSE:

THE PRIMARY GOAL OF THE WEBSITE CARBON CALCULATOR IS TO MAKE THE WEB MORE SUSTAINABLE BY INFORMING USERS ABOUT THE CARBON EMISSIONS OF THEIR WEBSITES AND PROVIDING ACTIONABLE STEPS TO REDUCE THEM. THIS INITIATIVE SEEKS TO HIGHLIGHT THE OFTEN-OVERLOOKED ENVIRONMENTAL COST OF DIGITAL ACTIVITIES, EMPHASIZING THE NEED FOR A MORE ECO-FRIENDLY WEB INFRASTRUCTURE.

OBJECTIVES:

RAISE AWARENESS: INCREASE UNDERSTANDING OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSOCIATED WITH WEBSITE USAGE, HELPING USERS RECOGNIZE THAT EVEN DIGITAL ACTIVITIES CONTRIBUTE TO CARBON EMISSIONS.

PROMOTE ENERGY-EFFICIENT WEB DESIGN: ENCOURAGE WEB DESIGNERS, DEVELOPERS, AND COMPANIES TO IMPLEMENT MORE SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES IN THE CREATION AND MAINTENANCE OF WEBSITES, SUCH AS OPTIMIZING FILE SIZES, UTILIZING GREEN HOSTING SOLUTIONS, AND MINIMIZING ENERGY CONSUMPTION.

BENCHMARK AND IMPROVE SUSTAINABILITY: PROVIDE TOOLS TO ASSESS A WEBSITE’S SUSTAINABILITY PERFORMANCE AND OFFER TARGETED RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT, ENABLING BUSINESSES TO MAKE INFORMED DECISIONS THAT ALIGN WITH THEIR ENVIRONMENTAL GOALS.

KEY FUNCTIONALITIES:

CO2 EMISSION CALCULATION: THE PLATFORM ANALYZES A WEBSITE’S ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND PROVIDES AN ESTIMATE OF THE CARBON DIOXIDE EMISSIONS GENERATED DURING THE LOADING OF THE PAGE.

SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT: THE TOOL EVALUATES THE SUSTAINABILITY OF A WEBSITE BY CONSIDERING VARIOUS PERFORMANCE INDICATORS, INCLUDING FILE SIZE, ENERGY REQUIRED FOR PAGE LOADING, AND WHETHER THE HOSTING PROVIDER IS POWERED BY RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES.

PERFORMANCE COMPARISON: USERS CAN COMPARE THEIR WEBSITE’S CARBON FOOTPRINT AGAINST INDUSTRY AVERAGES OR SIMILAR WEBSITES TO UNDERSTAND WHETHER THEIR SITE IS PERFORMING ABOVE OR BELOW THE ENVIRONMENTAL BENCHMARK. THIS COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS MOTIVATES USERS TO STRIVE FOR A LOWER CARBON FOOTPRINT.

PRACTICAL OPTIMIZATION SUGGESTIONS: THE PLATFORM PROVIDES PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR REDUCING ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND EMISSIONS, SUCH AS MINIMIZING IMAGE SIZES, COMPRESSING FILES, REDUCING SERVER REQUESTS, AND SWITCHING TO ECO-FRIENDLY HOSTING PROVIDERS. THESE SUGGESTIONS ARE TAILORED TO THE SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ANALYZED WEBSITE, MAKING THEM HIGHLY RELEVANT AND ACTIONABLE.

THE DIGITAL UPCYCLING PROJECT

THE DIGITAL UPCYCLING PROJECT BY TILDA IS AN INNOVATIVE INITIATIVE THAT MERGES PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL SUSTAINABILITY BY CREATING A COLLECTION OF GARMENTS USING DISCARDED MATERIALS—BOTH TANGIBLE AND DIGITAL. LAUNCHED IN THE METAVERSE ON WORLD ENVIRONMENT DAY (JUNE 5, 2022), THE PROJECT SEEKS TO RAISE AWARENESS ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF WASTE, PARTICULARLY TARGETING YOUNGER GENERATIONS TO PROMOTE RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND SUSTAINABLE DESIGN.

PURPOSE:

THE PRIMARY AIM OF THE DIGITAL UPCYCLING PROJECT IS TO HIGHLIGHT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF BOTH PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL WASTE WHILE DEMONSTRATING THE POTENTIAL FOR CREATIVE REUSE. THE COLLECTION UNDERSCORES THE OFTEN-OVERLOOKED ISSUE OF DIGITAL WASTE—DATA THAT IS GENERATED BUT REMAINS UNUSED—BY TRANSFORMING IT INTO VALUABLE AND MEANINGFUL DESIGN ELEMENTS.

OBJECTIVES:

RAISE AWARENESS OF DIGITAL AND PHYSICAL WASTE: EDUCATE THE PUBLIC, ESPECIALLY YOUNGER AUDIENCES, ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES OF DIGITAL WASTE (E.G., UNUSED DATA) AND PHYSICAL WASTE (E.G., DISCARDED FABRICS) AND HOW THEY CONTRIBUTE TO THE DEPLETION OF RESOURCES AND INCREASED CARBON EMISSIONS.
 PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE DESIGN: ADVOCATE FOR A MORE SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TO FASHION AND DESIGN BY CREATIVELY REUSING DISCARDED MATERIALS, THUS REDUCING THE NEED FOR NEW RESOURCES AND MINIMIZING WASTE.
 ENCOURAGE CREATIVE REUSE: DEMONSTRATE HOW DIGITAL AND PHYSICAL WASTE CAN BE UPCYCLED INTO UNIQUE, HIGH-QUALITY PRODUCTS, INSPIRING OTHER DESIGNERS AND INDUSTRIES TO EXPLORE SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES AND RETHINK THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH DISCARDED MATERIALS.

KEY ELEMENTS OF THE PROJECT:

MATERIAL SOURCES:
 PHYSICAL MATERIALS: THE GARMENTS WERE CRAFTED USING SECOND-HAND DENIM AND REPURPOSED FABRICS. THIS CHOICE NOT ONLY REDUCES TEXTILE WASTE BUT ALSO ALIGNS WITH SUSTAINABLE FASHION PRINCIPLES.
 DIGITAL MATERIALS: THE PROJECT UTILIZED UNUSED DIGITAL ASSETS—IMAGES GENERATED BY AI DURING THE DESIGN PROCESS OF A PREVIOUS COLLECTION. OF THE 4,000 DIGITAL IMAGES CREATED, ONLY 13 WERE USED, WHILE THE REST WERE CONSIDERED “DIGITAL WASTE.” THESE DISCARDED IMAGES WERE THEN REINTERPRETED AND TRANSFORMED INTO UNIQUE PATTERNS AND MOTIFS FOR THE COLLECTION.

ADDRESSED ISSUES:

THE PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS HOW DIGITAL WASTE, LIKE PHYSICAL WASTE, ACCUMULATES IN THE FORM OF UNUSED AND UNNECESSARY DATA. THIS DATA CONTINUES TO OCCUPY STORAGE SPACE, REQUIRING ENERGY TO BE MAINTAINED, AND CONTRIBUTES TO CARBON EMISSIONS. FOR INSTANCE, RESEARCH FROM THE LG AI TEAM INDICATES THAT THE ANNUAL CO2 EMISSIONS FROM THE EMAIL TRAFFIC OF A SINGLE OFFICE WORKER CAN BE EQUIVALENT TO THOSE PRODUCED BY A LARGE VEHICLE TRAVELING 200 MILES.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT:

BY REPURPOSING BOTH PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL WASTE, THE PROJECT MITIGATES THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSOCIATED WITH THE PRODUCTION OF NEW MATERIALS AND THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION NEEDED TO STORE DIGITAL DATA. THE COLLECTION SERVES AS A TANGIBLE REMINDER OF HOW REDUCING WASTE AT ALL LEVELS—BE IT TEXTILE OR DATA—CAN CONTRIBUTE TO A LOWER ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT.

REPURPOSING BITS AND PIECES OF THE DIGITAL PROJECT

THE REPURPOSING BITS AND PIECES OF THE DIGITAL PROJECT EXPLORES INNOVATIVE WAYS TO TRANSFORM DISCARDED DIGITAL MATERIALS INTO NEW, MEANINGFUL FORMS OF EXPRESSION. THROUGH ITS CORE APPLICATION, DELETE BY HAIKU, THE PROJECT CREATIVELY REPURPOSES UNUSED TEXT MESSAGES INTO HAIKU POEMS, OFFERING A FRESH PERSPECTIVE ON HOW DIGITAL WASTE CAN BE REIMAGINED AND GIVEN NEW VALUE.

PURPOSE:

THE PRIMARY AIM OF THE PROJECT IS TO RAISE AWARENESS ABOUT THE ACCUMULATION OF DIGITAL WASTE AND ITS IMPLICATIONS, WHILE SIMULTANEOUSLY SHOWCASING THE POTENTIAL FOR CREATIVE REUSE. BY CONVERTING DISCARDED DIGITAL DATA INTO POETRY, THE PROJECT CHALLENGES TRADITIONAL NOTIONS OF WHAT CONSTITUTES WASTE AND PROMOTES A MORE THOUGHTFUL APPROACH TO DIGITAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT.

OBJECTIVES:

CREATIVE REUSE OF DIGITAL DATA: DEMONSTRATE HOW SEEMINGLY TRIVIAL OR OBSOLETE DIGITAL MATERIALS, SUCH AS OLD TEXT MESSAGES, CAN BE CREATIVELY REPURPOSED INTO ARTISTIC EXPRESSIONS, FOSTERING A DEEPER APPRECIATION FOR DIGITAL CONTENT AND ITS POTENTIAL BEYOND INITIAL USE.
 RAISE AWARENESS OF DIGITAL WASTE: HIGHLIGHT THE GROWING ISSUE OF DIGITAL WASTE ACCUMULATION—UNUSED OR UNNECESSARY DATA THAT TAKES UP STORAGE SPACE AND REQUIRES ENERGY TO MAINTAIN. THE PROJECT AIMS TO BRING ATTENTION TO THIS OFTEN-OVERLOOKED ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERN.
 INNOVATIVE INTERACTION DESIGN: EXPLORE THE INTERSECTION OF ART AND SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH INTERACTION DESIGN, USING CREATIVE APPROACHES TO ENGAGE USERS IN A REFLECTION ON THEIR OWN DIGITAL CONSUMPTION HABITS AND THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF STORING UNUSED DATA.

KEY STRATEGIES AND THEMES:

DIGITAL DATA UPCYCLING: THE PROJECT EMBRACES THE CONCEPT OF UPCYCLING IN THE DIGITAL REALM BY TRANSFORMING DISCARDED DIGITAL MESSAGES INTO HAIKU POEMS. THIS PROCESS NOT ONLY GIVES NEW LIFE TO OTHERWISE FORGOTTEN DATA BUT ALSO EMPHASIZES THE POTENTIAL FOR CREATIVE REINTERPRETATION OF DIGITAL CONTENT.
 COMBINING ART AND SUSTAINABILITY: BY BLENDING ART AND SUSTAINABILITY, THE PROJECT PROVIDES A UNIQUE APPROACH TO DIGITAL INTERACTION. IT ENCOURAGES USERS TO RETHINK THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH DIGITAL CONTENT AND INVITES THEM TO PARTICIPATE IN THE CREATIVE PROCESS OF TURNING WASTE INTO ART.
 AWARENESS THROUGH INTERACTION: THE DELETE BY HAIKU APP SERVES AS AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL, ALLOWING USERS TO EXPERIENCE FIRSTHAND HOW THEIR DISCARDED MESSAGES CAN BE TRANSFORMED INTO SOMETHING NEW AND MEANINGFUL. THIS INTERACTION PROMOTES A MORE CONSCIOUS APPROACH TO DIGITAL DATA MANAGEMENT.

DDUMP

DDUMP, CREATED BY LOREDANA BONTEMPI IN 2010, IS A DIGITAL REPOSITORY THAT PROVIDES A PLATFORM FOR USERS TO SHARE AND REPURPOSE THEIR “DIGITAL WASTE,” SUCH AS UNUSED OR DISCARDED FILES. BY ALLOWING USERS TO DRAG THESE FILES INTO A VIRTUAL “TRASH BIN,” THE PROJECT TRANSFORMS DIGITAL REFUSE INTO A COLLECTIVE ONLINE RESOURCE, PROMOTING A MORE SUSTAINABLE AND THOUGHTFUL APPROACH TO DIGITAL CONTENT MANAGEMENT.

PURPOSE:

THE PRIMARY OBJECTIVE OF DDUMP IS TO RAISE AWARENESS ABOUT THE ACCUMULATION OF DIGITAL WASTE AND TO ENCOURAGE ITS CREATIVE REUSE. THE PROJECT REFRAMES DISCARDED DIGITAL CONTENT NOT AS USELESS WASTE, BUT AS A VALUABLE RESOURCE THAT CAN BE SHARED AND REPURPOSED WITHIN A COMMUNITY. IT AIMS TO FOSTER A REFLECTION ON THE LIFECYCLE OF DIGITAL DATA AND HIGHLIGHT THE POTENTIAL FOR GIVING NEW MEANING AND UTILITY TO WHAT WOULD OTHERWISE BE DELETED AND FORGOTTEN.

OBJECTIVES:

RAISE AWARENESS OF DIGITAL WASTE: BRING ATTENTION TO THE OFTEN-OVERLOOKED ISSUE OF DIGITAL WASTE—UNUSED FILES AND DATA THAT CONTINUE TO OCCUPY STORAGE SPACE AND REQUIRE ENERGY FOR MAINTENANCE—BY MAKING THESE FILES VISIBLE AND SHARABLE THROUGH A COLLECTIVE DIGITAL REPOSITORY.
PROMOTE CREATIVE REUSE: ENCOURAGE USERS TO RETHINK HOW THEY HANDLE DIGITAL FILES AND CONSIDER WAYS TO REPURPOSE OR SHARE DISCARDED CONTENT. THIS APPROACH NOT ONLY PREVENTS THE UNNECESSARY ACCUMULATION OF DATA BUT ALSO OPENS UP NEW POSSIBILITIES FOR CREATIVE AND COLLABORATIVE PROJECTS.
CREATE A SHARED DIGITAL RESOURCE: ESTABLISH A COMMUNAL REPOSITORY WHERE DISCARDED FILES CAN BE STORED, ACCESSED, AND REUSED BY OTHERS. THIS SHARED SPACE TRANSFORMS INDIVIDUAL DIGITAL WASTE INTO A COLLECTIVE RESOURCE, FOSTERING COLLABORATION AND SHARED CREATIVITY.

KEY FUNCTIONALITIES:

DIGITAL WASTE REPOSITORY: DDUMP SERVES AS A DIGITAL “TRASH BIN” WHERE USERS CAN UPLOAD THEIR UNWANTED FILES—SUCH AS OLD DOCUMENTS, UNUSED IMAGES, OR DISCARDED DESIGN ELEMENTS. THESE FILES ARE THEN STORED IN A SHARED ONLINE SPACE, MAKING THEM AVAILABLE FOR OTHERS TO EXPLORE AND REPURPOSE.
COLLECTIVE SHARING AND REUSE: THE PLATFORM FACILITATES THE COLLECTIVE SHARING OF DIGITAL WASTE, ALLOWING USERS TO BROWSE THE REPOSITORY AND FIND NEW USES FOR CONTENT THAT WOULD OTHERWISE BE DISCARDED. THIS COLLABORATIVE APPROACH HELPS REDUCE REDUNDANT DATA CREATION AND ENCOURAGES A MORE RESOURCE-EFFICIENT USE OF DIGITAL CONTENT.
REFLECTION ON DATA LIFECYCLE: BY VISUALIZING THE ACCUMULATION AND SHARING OF DIGITAL WASTE, DDUMP PROMPTS USERS TO REFLECT ON THE LIFECYCLE OF THEIR DATA. THE PLATFORM ENCOURAGES A MORE MINDFUL APPROACH TO DIGITAL CONTENT MANAGEMENT, EMPHASIZING THE IMPORTANCE OF CONSIDERING WHAT HAPPENS TO FILES AFTER THEY ARE NO LONGER NEEDED.

Expertise interview

A.5.7

Given the strong relevance of the Ddump project to research on digital consumption, an interview was conducted with Loredana Bontempi to gain deeper insights into the project’s goals, methodologies, and implications. This conversation aimed to explore how the project addresses critical issues related to sustainable practices, the environmental impact of digital technologies, and the creative reuse of generative waste.

LOREDANA BONTEMPI

LOREDANA BONTEMPI, CO-FOUNDER OF PARCO STUDIO, A CONTENT-FIRST DESIGN STUDIO BASED IN MILAN, OFFERS A UNIQUE PERSPECTIVE ON DIGITAL SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH HER DDUMP PROJECT. HER INITIATIVE, WHICH INVITES USERS TO SHARE AND CREATIVELY REPURPOSE DIGITAL WASTE, BRIDGES THE GAP BETWEEN PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL SUSTAINABILITY BY APPLYING PRINCIPLES OF RECYCLING AND REUSE TO THE DIGITAL REALM. BONTEMPI’S APPROACH HIGHLIGHTS THE EXPRESSIVE POTENTIAL OF DISCARDED DIGITAL CONTENT AND BRINGS ATTENTION TO THE OFTEN-OVERLOOKED ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DAILY DIGITAL ACTIONS.

KEY FINDINGS

>TRANSFORMING DIGITAL WASTE INTO CREATIVE EXPRESSION:

LOREDANA EMPHASIZED HOW DISCARDED DIGITAL CONTENT, SUCH AS UNUSED FILES OR IMAGES GENERATED DURING DESIGN PROCESSES, CAN BE REPURPOSED TO CREATE NEW FORMS OF EXPRESSION. BY EMBRACING IMPERFECTIONS AND WORKING WITH MATERIALS TYPICALLY CONSIDERED WASTE, THE DDUMP PROJECT SHOWS HOW DIGITAL REFUSE CAN BE TURNED INTO VALUABLE ARTISTIC CONTENT. THIS APPROACH CHALLENGES CONVENTIONAL VIEWS ON THE VALUE OF DIGITAL MATERIALS, HIGHLIGHTING THE POTENTIAL OF DIGITAL UPCYCLING TO FOSTER CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION.

>LACK OF AWARENESS ABOUT DIGITAL WASTE AND ITS IMPACT:

THERE IS A WIDESPREAD LACK OF UNDERSTANDING REGARDING THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF EVERYDAY DIGITAL ACTIVITIES, SUCH AS STORING FILES, SENDING EMAILS, OR BACKING UP DATA. DESPITE THE AVAILABILITY OF TOOLS TO MEASURE THE ENERGY IMPACT OF THESE ACTIONS, BONTEMPI NOTED THAT COMMUNICATING THIS REALITY TO THE PUBLIC IS OFTEN MET WITH SKEPTICISM OR DISMISSAL. PEOPLE TEND TO VIEW THOSE RAISING THESE CONCERNS AS OVERLY ALARMIST, MAKING IT DIFFICULT TO ENGAGE THE PUBLIC IN CONVERSATIONS ABOUT DIGITAL SUSTAINABILITY.

>INCREASING VISIBILITY OF DIGITAL SUSTAINABILITY:

BONTEMPI STRESSED THE NEED TO MAKE INFORMATION ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DIGITAL ACTIVITIES MORE VISIBLE AND ACCESSIBLE TO THE PUBLIC. SHE BELIEVES THAT MAKING DATA ON DIGITAL WASTE AND ENERGY USAGE MORE TRANSPARENT COULD ENCOURAGE INDIVIDUALS TO ADOPT MORE RESPONSIBLE DIGITAL PRACTICES. PROMOTING A MINIMALIST AND CONSCIOUS APPROACH TO DIGITAL CONSUMPTION COULD REDUCE UNNECESSARY DATA GENERATION AND MITIGATE ITS ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT.

>INTEGRATING PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL RECYCLING PRINCIPLES:

THE DDUMP PROJECT ORIGINATED FROM A PERSONAL REFLECTION ON THE LARGE VOLUME OF DIGITAL CONTENT BONTEMPI WAS PRODUCING AND MANAGING. INSPIRED BY TRADITIONAL RECYCLING PRINCIPLES USED TO HANDLE PHYSICAL WASTE, SHE SOUGHT TO APPLY THESE CONCEPTS TO THE DIGITAL WORLD BY REUSING AND REPURPOSING UNUSED FILES INSTEAD OF MERELY DELETING THEM. THIS APPROACH CONNECTS THE MANAGEMENT OF PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL RESOURCES, SUGGESTING A HOLISTIC VIEW OF SUSTAINABILITY THAT TRANSCENDS TRADITIONAL BOUNDARIES.

KEY INSIGHTS

THE INSIGHTS FROM LOREDANA BONTEMPI FOCUS ON REDEFINING THE CONCEPT OF DIGITAL WASTE AND EXPLORING HOW CREATIVE REUSE CAN TRANSFORM IT INTO VALUABLE RESOURCES. THROUGH HER DDUMP PROJECT, BONTEMPI CHALLENGES THE TRADITIONAL VIEW OF DIGITAL WASTE AS MERE CLUTTER TO BE DISCARDED, HIGHLIGHTING THE ARTISTIC AND EXPRESSIVE POTENTIAL OF UNWANTED DIGITAL FILES. HER WORK BRIDGES THE GAP BETWEEN PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL RECYCLING, DEMONSTRATING THAT BOTH REALMS CAN BENEFIT FROM SIMILAR SUSTAINABLE PRINCIPLES. ADDITIONALLY, BONTEMPI EMPHASIZES THE NEED TO RAISE AWARENESS OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DIGITAL ACTIONS, PROMOTING A MORE MINDFUL AND MINIMALIST APPROACH TO DIGITAL CONSUMPTION. THE KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM THE INTERVIEW WITH LOREDANA BONTEMPI ARE:

>REDEFINE DIGITAL WASTE AS A CREATIVE RESOURCE: ENCOURAGE THE PERCEPTION OF DIGITAL WASTE AS A RESOURCE THAT CAN BE REPURPOSED FOR CREATIVE AND MEANINGFUL EXPRESSIONS, RATHER THAN SOMETHING TO BE DISCARDED. THIS APPROACH EMPHASIZES THE POTENTIAL FOR UPCYCLING DIGITAL CONTENT INTO VALUABLE ASSETS.

>INTEGRATE PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL RECYCLING PRACTICES: APPLY PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL RECYCLING TO DIGITAL CONTENT MANAGEMENT, PROMOTING A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO SUSTAINABILITY THAT VIEWS PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL WASTE AS INTERCONNECTED ISSUES REQUIRING UNIFIED STRATEGIES.

>PROMOTE DIGITAL MINIMALISM THROUGH AWARENESS: INCREASE PUBLIC AWARENESS ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DIGITAL WASTE AND ENCOURAGE INDIVIDUALS TO ADOPT A MORE CONSCIOUS AND MINIMALISTIC APPROACH TO THEIR DIGITAL ACTIVITIES, REDUCING UNNECESSARY DATA STORAGE AND CONSUMPTION.

Case studies benchmark analysis

A.5.8

[FIG 10]

Case studies benchmark analysis

A.5.8

The analysis of the case studies is based on two primary factors that help position each project within the broader landscape of digital waste management and sustainability efforts. These factors are:

Purpose of the Service:

> Practical Services:

Tools like the Website Carbon Calculator and Digital Waste Project focus on reducing digital waste and promoting sustainability through functional solutions.

> Speculative/Artistic Projects:

Initiatives like Delete by Haiku and Ddump repurpose digital waste for creative expression, exploring the artistic potential of discarded content.

Raising Awareness vs. Applying Sustainable Practices:

> Raising Awareness:

Projects such as Ecologia Digitale and Website Carbon Calculator educate users about the environmental impact of digital activities.

> Applying Sustainable Practices: The Digital

Upcycling Project and Ddump focus on creatively reusing digital waste, promoting sustainable digital consumption.

Key Insights

Practical Services Focus on Awareness:

Tools like the Website Carbon Calculator mainly educate users about the environmental impact of digital activities, helping them make informed choices to reduce their digital carbon footprint.

Speculative Projects Apply Sustainable Practices:

Projects like Delete by Haiku and Ddump focus on creatively reusing digital waste, promoting sustainable practices through artistic repurposing.

Balanced Approaches:

Initiatives like the Digital Waste Project combine awareness and action, providing both tools for waste management and education about digital consumption's environmental effects.

Conclusion

The benchmark highlights two main trends: practical services raise awareness, while speculative projects apply sustainability by reusing digital materials. Our project aims to bridge these areas by repurposing AI-generated waste, promoting both awareness and practical sustainability.

Tangible sustainable methodologies

A.5.9

Reduce:

Minimizing waste and resource consumption by adopting behavioral guidelines that can be followed both individually and collectively.

Reuse:

Recovering and repurposing products before they become waste. Reuse involves taking immediate action to restore an item's function, preventing it from turning into garbage.

Recycle:

Transforming waste materials through industrial processes into new raw materials that can be reintegrated into the production cycle.

Collect:

Waste separation. Citizens play a crucial role in this process by properly disposing of waste in designated bins, following local regulations. The goal is to reduce the final volume of waste sent to landfills while conserving raw materials and energy.

Recover:

Energy recovery. It's possible to recover energy through the disposal of certain materials.(Camec, n.d.)[25]

These concepts primarily apply to tangible sustainability practices, but how can we adapt them to the digital world? After evaluating several methods, those most suitable for digital realism and generative content have been selected:

- > Reduce
- > Reuse
- > Recycle
- > Collect

Recover has been excluded because in a generative and digital realism there are no information on how to transform digital energy.

Digital sustainable methodologies

A.5.10

To create a tailored language to apply as sustainable methodologies in the digital realism those terms have been changed in order to better represent the digital realism:

BitShrink:

Focused on minimizing the amount of data and digital resources by compressing information, optimizing storage, and reducing digital waste. This term conveys the idea of shrinking data footprints and cutting down on unnecessary bits in digital processes.

Rethink:

This term conveys the idea of taking existing digital assets, and adapting or modifying them for new uses. It involves using creative thinking to adapt what already exists for a different purpose, without major structural changes.

Recode:

Transforming outdated or redundant digital materials through restructuring or reprogramming to reintegrate them into the digital ecosystem. Emphasizes the technical transformation of outdated or redundant digital materials.

Curate:

Organizing and managing digital content and data, ensuring proper categorization and archiving to streamline future usage and reduce digital clutter.

Conclusion

A.5.11

The environmental impact of GenAI is a pressing issue, and as individuals, it's challenging to address the problem at its root. Therefore, the project must focus on how the public uses these AI models to implement digital sustainability practices. Digital realism urgently needs to adopt better sustainable strategies that encourage individuals to take a more mindful approach. Although some initiatives have been introduced to raise awareness about the ecological footprint of digital actions, the issue—particularly in terms of GenAI consumption—has not been effectively communicated to the public.

When discussing applied digital sustainability practices, case studies like “Ddump” and “The Digital Upcycling Project” illustrate that efforts such as recycling digital materials often serve speculative or artistic purposes. This highlights the lack of accessible services that can help people grasp the problem more fully and inspire action, such as BitShrinking while also provide individuals with access to digital waste materials, especially generative waste, empowering them to Curate, Rethink, and Recode it.

The use of GenAI to spark creativity in the design field

A.5.12

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) has become a significant focus of research and practice in design, offering new possibilities for creativity, innovation, and collaboration. The integration of GenAI into the design process, particularly in the initial ideation and final refinement stages, is emerging as a novel approach to co-creation, where both human designers and AI contribute proactively. (Yannakakis et.al, 2014)[26] This interaction fosters lateral thinking and provides unexpected stimuli that can lead to innovative solutions. (Van Der Maden et.al, 2023) [27]

Survey

A.5.13

TO BETTER ADDRESS THE TOPIC OF THE USE OF GENAI IN THE DESIGN FIELD A SURVEY WAS DELIVERED TO DESIGN STUDENTS. THE SURVEY AIMED TO BETTER UNDERSTAND THE USE OF GENAI FOR DESIGNERS AND THE PHASES OF APPLICATION, THE AWARENESS ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF GENAI AND THE OPINION ON GENERATIVE WASTE CONTENT.

LEARNING OBJECTIVES

THE OBJECTIVE OF THE SURVEY WAS TO GAIN INSIGHTS INTO THE USE OF GENERATIVE AI AMONG DESIGN STUDENTS AND PROFESSIONALS. THE SURVEY AIMED TO ADDRESS THE FOLLOWING POINTS:

UNDERSTAND WHY DESIGN STUDENTS AND PROFESSIONALS PRIMARILY USE GENERATIVE AI.

IDENTIFY THE KEY FEATURES OF GENERATIVE AI THAT USERS FIND INDISPENSABLE.

DETERMINE WHICH AI TOOLS AND CONTENT TYPES ARE MOST BENEFICIAL FOR DESIGNERS.

ASSESS AWARENESS REGARDING THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF GENERATIVE AI.

UNDERSTAND THE PERCEPTION OF "GENERATIVE WASTE" AND STRATEGIES TO ADDRESS IT.

TARGET AUDIENCE

THE SURVEY TARGETED DESIGN STUDENTS AND PROFESSIONALS, WITH A TOTAL OF 30 RESPONDENTS. THE AREAS OF DESIGN COVERED INCLUDE:

- > GRAPHIC DESIGN: 40%
- > UI/UX DESIGN: 50%
- > PRODUCT DESIGN: 30%

IN TERMS OF FAMILIARITY WITH AI:

- > 96.6% ARE FAMILIAR WITH AI.
- > 3.3% ARE NOT FAMILIAR WITH AI.

KEY INSIGHTS

GENERATIVE AI USAGE:

RESPONDENTS PRIMARILY USE TOOLS SUCH AS CHATGPT, MIDJOURNEY, AND DALL-E FOR ACTIVITIES SUCH AS:

- > BRAINSTORMING.
- > VISUAL CONTENT CREATION.
- > PROTOTYPING.
- > CREATIVE ITERATION AND REFINEMENT.

KEY FEATURES THAT DRIVE AI ADOPTION:

THE MAIN QUALITIES OF AI THAT MOTIVATE RESPONDENTS TO USE IT INCLUDE:

- > SPEED IN OBTAINING RESULTS.
- > CREATIVE POSSIBILITIES OFFERED BY AI.
- > ACCESS TO RESOURCES THAT ARE OTHERWISE DIFFICULT OR IMPOSSIBLE TO OBTAIN.

ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS:

AWARENESS REGARDING THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF AI IS RELATIVELY LOW, AS ONLY 23% OF PARTICIPANTS KNOW ABOUT THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION ASSOCIATED WITH GENERATING AN IMAGE. HOWEVER, 63% EXPRESSED CONCERN ABOUT THE POTENTIAL ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF USING AI. THIS INDICATES A SIGNIFICANT OPPORTUNITY TO BRIDGE THE INFORMATION GAP REGARDING THE ECOLOGICAL FOOTPRINT OF AI TOOLS, AS DESIGNERS SHOW AN INHERENT INTEREST IN SUSTAINABILITY.

GENERATIVE WASTE MANAGEMENT:

THE STRATEGIES THAT DESIGNERS HIGHLIGHTED TO MINIMIZE "GENERATIVE WASTE" INCLUDE:

- > RAISING AWARENESS ABOUT AI'S ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT.
- > IMPLEMENTING SUSTAINABILITY FEATURES IN AI TOOLS.
- > ENCOURAGING THE CREATIVE REUSE OF "GENERATIVE WASTE."

FREQUENCY OF AI OUTPUT DISCARDING:

A SUBSTANTIAL 73.3% OF RESPONDENTS DISCARD AI-GENERATED OUTPUTS QUITE FREQUENTLY OR VERY FREQUENTLY DUE TO:

- > VISUAL ERRORS OR INCONSISTENCIES.
- > LACK OF RELEVANCE TO PROJECT OBJECTIVES.

LACK OF REUSE AWARENESS:

APPROXIMATELY 80% OF THESE RESPONDENTS HAVE NEVER CONSIDERED REUSING AI-GENERATED WASTE DUE TO THE AFOREMENTIONED REASONS, AS WELL AS A LACK OF KNOWLEDGE ON HOW TO CREATIVELY REPURPOSE SUCH CONTENT. HOWEVER, 75% OF THEM EXPRESSED INTEREST IN EXPLORING CREATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR REUSING GENERATIVE WASTE.

KEY OPPORTUNITIES

THE FINDINGS INDICATE SEVERAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR ADDRESSING GAPS AND DEVELOPING USER-CENTERED SOLUTIONS:

INCREASE AWARENESS:

DEVELOP EDUCATIONAL CONTENT AND RESOURCES TO INFORM USERS ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF GENERATIVE AI TOOLS AND HOW THEY CAN MAKE MORE SUSTAINABLE CHOICES.

ENCOURAGE CREATIVE REUSE:

CREATE PLATFORMS OR INITIATIVES THAT SHOWCASE CREATIVE WAYS TO REPURPOSE AND RECYCLE GENERATIVE WASTE. THIS COULD INCLUDE WORKSHOPS, ONLINE COMMUNITIES, OR TOOL INTEGRATIONS THAT FACILITATE THE CREATIVE TRANSFORMATION OF DISCARDED OUTPUTS.

INTEGRATE SUSTAINABILITY FEATURES:

ADVOCATE FOR SUSTAINABILITY FEATURES WITHIN AI TOOLS THAT COULD HELP MINIMIZE ENERGY CONSUMPTION, OPTIMIZE USAGE, AND OFFER INSIGHTS INTO THE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT OF VARIOUS GENERATIVE PROCESSES.

BY ADDRESSING THESE AREAS, IT IS POSSIBLE TO BUILD A MORE INFORMED AND CONSCIOUS DESIGN COMMUNITY THAT LEVERAGES THE POWER OF GENERATIVE AI WHILE MITIGATING ITS NEGATIVE IMPACTS AND MAXIMIZING ITS CREATIVE POTENTIAL.

Interviews with
designers

A.5.14

TO FURTHER ENHANCE THE RESEARCH AND GAIN A DEEPER UNDERSTANDING OF USER NEEDS, A GROUP INTERVIEW WAS CONDUCTED WITH THREE DESIGNERS. THE AIM WAS TO EXPLORE THE ROLE OF GENERATIVE AI IN THEIR CREATIVE WORKFLOWS AND PINPOINT SPECIFIC AREAS WHERE ADDITIONAL SUPPORT OR IMPROVEMENTS ARE REQUIRED. THIS QUALITATIVE APPROACH PROVIDED VALUABLE INSIGHTS, ENABLING A MORE PRECISE ALIGNMENT WITH THE DESIGNERS' EXPECTATIONS AND CHALLENGES WHEN USING GENERATIVE AI TOOLS. THE INTERVIEW SPECIFICALLY TARGETED VISUAL DESIGNERS, AS THEY REPRESENT A SIGNIFICANT PORTION OF THE DESIGN DISCIPLINES COVERED IN THE SURVEY RESPONSES.

LEARNING OBJECTIVES

THE OBJECTIVE OF THE INTERVIEW WAS TO GAIN INSIGHTS INTO THE USE OF GENERATIVE AI AMONG DESIGN STUDENTS. THE INTERVIEW AIMED TO ADDRESS THE FOLLOWING POINTS:

UNDERSTAND HOW DESIGNERS USE AND INTEGRATE GENERATIVE AI IN THEIR CREATIVE PROCESSES;

IDENTIFY WHICH AI TOOLS ARE MOST FREQUENTLY USED, IN WHICH STAGES OF THE DESIGN PROCESS THEY ARE APPLIED, AND FOR WHAT SPECIFIC PURPOSES (E.G., IDEATION, CONTENT CREATION, PROTOTYPING);

IDENTIFY BARRIERS AND MOTIVATIONS FOR USING OR ABANDONING GENERATIVE AI TOOLS;

EXPLORE THE REASONS BEHIND ADOPTING OR DISCONTINUING AI TOOLS, INCLUDING FACTORS SUCH AS COST, USABILITY, OUTPUT QUALITY, AND ALIGNMENT WITH PROJECT NEEDS;

DETERMINE THE EXPECTATIONS AND DESIRED OUTCOMES FROM AI-GENERATED CONTENT;

UNDERSTAND WHAT TYPES OF RESULTS DESIGNERS SEEK FROM AI TOOLS AND HOW THESE OUTPUTS INFLUENCE THEIR CREATIVE DECISION-MAKING AND PROJECT OUTCOMES;

EVALUATE DESIGNERS' AWARENESS AND PERCEPTIONS OF GENERATIVE AI WASTE AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT;

ASSESS THEIR KNOWLEDGE AND CONCERN REGARDING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AI USAGE, AND EXPLORE POTENTIAL STRATEGIES TO MINIMIZE GENERATIVE WASTE;

KEY FINDINGS

> PROMPT COMPLEXITY AS A BARRIER FOR DESIGNERS:

DESIGNERS OFTEN STRUGGLE WITH THE COMPLEXITY OF CRAFTING PRECISE PROMPTS REQUIRED BY GENERATIVE AI TOOLS. THIS DIFFICULTY ARISES BECAUSE IT IS CHALLENGING FOR THEM TO TRANSLATE ABSTRACT VISUAL CONCEPTS INTO DETAILED TEXT-BASED INSTRUCTIONS. CONSEQUENTLY, THIS LEADS TO A HIGHER RATE OF DISCARDED OUTPUTS, AS THE RESULTS FREQUENTLY DO NOT ALIGN WITH THEIR INITIAL VISUAL INTENTIONS.

> AI TOOLS USED PRIMARILY FOR IDEATION AND INSPIRATION, NOT FINAL OUTPUT CREATION:

DESIGNERS PREDOMINANTLY USE AI TOOLS AND DESKTOP APPLICATIONS LIKE PINTEREST, BEHANCE, AND INSTAGRAM AS IMAGE CONTENT AGGREGATORS DURING THE IDEATION PHASE, TO GATHER INSPIRATION AND EXPLORE VISUAL TRENDS. HOWEVER, THEY RARELY RELY ON AI FOR CREATING FINAL VISUAL OUTPUTS, AS THERE IS STILL A LACK OF CONFIDENCE IN USING AI FOR CONTENT PRODUCTION AT THIS STAGE OF THE CREATIVE PROCESS.

> MAIN DRIVERS FOR USING AI TOOLS:

THE PRIMARY MOTIVATIONS FOR USING AI TOOLS INCLUDE: DIFFICULTY IN FINDING ONLINE CONTENT THAT MATCHES THE VISUAL POTENTIAL OF GENERATIVE OUTPUTS, THE ABILITY OF AI TO PRODUCE VISUALLY INTRIGUING AND UNEXPECTED RESULTS THAT ARE HARD TO ACHIEVE THROUGH TRADITIONAL MEANS.

> INTEREST IN IMPERFECT OUTPUTS:

THERE IS A HIGHER INTEREST IN EXPLORING IMPERFECT OUTPUTS GENERATED BY AI COMPARED TO ACHIEVING "PERFECT" RESULTS, AS DESIGNERS APPRECIATE THE CREATIVE POTENTIAL AND UNIQUE QUALITIES OF THESE IMPERFECTIONS.

> LIMITED AWARENESS AND CONCERN ABOUT DIGITAL WASTE:

DESIGNERS SHOW RELATIVELY LOW CONCERN FOR DIGITAL WASTE COMPARED TO TANGIBLE WASTE. A DEEPER INQUIRY REVEALED A LACK OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DIGITAL WASTE AND A PERCEPTION THAT INDIVIDUAL ACTIONS HAVE LIMITED INFLUENCE. THIS INDICATES AN OPPORTUNITY TO RAISE AWARENESS AND EDUCATE DESIGNERS ON THE IMPORTANCE OF SUSTAINABLE DIGITAL PRACTICES.

KEY INSIGHTS

> REDEFINING GENERATIVE WASTE AS A CREATIVE RESOURCE:

SHIFT THE PERCEPTION OF AI-GENERATED WASTE FROM A DISCARDED BYPRODUCT TO A VALUABLE SOURCE OF VISUAL MATERIAL THAT CAN INSPIRE NEW CREATIVE DIRECTIONS. THIS OPENS UP POSSIBILITIES FOR DEVELOPING TOOLS AND METHODOLOGIES THAT PROMOTE THE RE-USE AND REINTERPRETATION OF GENERATIVE WASTE, POSITIONING IT AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE CREATIVE PROCESS.

> CREATING VISUAL EXPLORATION METHODS BEYOND TEXT-BASED PROMPTS:

EXPLORE NEW INPUT MECHANISMS THAT GO BEYOND TRADITIONAL TEXT-BASED PROMPTS, SUCH AS SKETCH-BASED, IMAGE-BASED, OR INTERACTIVE VISUAL ADJUSTMENTS. THIS WOULD ENABLE MORE INTUITIVE INTERACTIONS, REDUCING THE RELIANCE ON TRIAL-AND-ERROR GENERATIONS, THUS MINIMIZING THE OVERALL AI CONSUMPTION WHILE FOSTERING SPONTANEOUS DISCOVERIES.

> INCORPORATING EDUCATIONAL ELEMENTS TO ENCOURAGE SUSTAINABLE AI PRACTICES:

EDUCATE DESIGNERS ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPLICATIONS OF AI USAGE AND EMPOWER THEM WITH TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES TO OPTIMIZE THEIR CREATIVE PROCESS. INCORPORATING FEATURES THAT HIGHLIGHT THE ENERGY COST OF EACH GENERATION OR OFFERING PROMPTS FOR REUSING EXISTING OUTPUTS CAN BUILD A CULTURE OF SUSTAINABILITY IN DIGITAL DESIGN.

AGNESE AZZOLA

AGNESE'S MASTER'S THESIS EXPLORES THE INTEGRATION OF AI-BASED IMAGE GENERATORS INTO INDUSTRIAL DESIGN. AFTER CONDUCTING A LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SUBJECT, SHE DEVELOPED A PROCESS MODEL THAT DEMONSTRATES HOW AI CAN BE INCORPORATED INTO THE PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT CYCLE. AGNESE TESTED THIS MODEL BY CREATING THREE PRODUCTS AND, IN THE END, FORMULATED GUIDELINES ON HOW TO EFFECTIVELY INTERACT WITH IMAGE GENERATORS, BOTH AT A GENERAL AND TECHNICAL LEVEL, TO OPTIMIZE CREATIVE OUTCOMES.

KEY FINDINGS

- > INSPIRATION FROM DETAILS
AGNESE HIGHLIGHTS HOW, IN THE PROCESS OF USING IMAGE GENERATORS TO CREATE A PRODUCT, IT IS OFTEN THE SMALL DETAILS—SUCH AS SPECIFIC FEATURES OR TEXTURES—THAT SPARK INSPIRATION AND GIVE RISE TO NEW IDEAS.
> OVERPRODUCTION OF IMAGES
THROUGHOUT HER PROJECT, AGNESE GENERATED A LARGE NUMBER OF IMAGES, DISCARDING MANY AND SELECTING ONLY THOSE THAT CAPTURED HER ATTENTION. THIS UNDERScoreD THE RISK OF GETTING LOST IN AN OVERPRODUCTION OF IMAGES, WITH THE MAJORITY ENDING UP FORGOTTEN OR UNUSED.
> NEED FOR A MINDFUL APPROACH
AGNESE EMPHASIZES THE IMPORTANCE OF ADOPTING A MORE INTENTIONAL AND FOCUSED APPROACH WHEN USING IMAGE GENERATORS, AVOIDING EXCESSIVE AND INDISCRIMINATE GENERATION THAT CAN BE INEFFECTIVE AND OVERWHELMING.

KEY INSIGHTS

- > THE POWER OF SMALL DETAILS
SMALL DETAILS, SUCH AS TEXTURES AND FEATURES, PLAY A CRUCIAL ROLE IN SPARKING NEW IDEAS DURING THE CREATIVE PROCESS. THESE ELEMENTS CAN INSPIRE INNOVATIVE DIRECTIONS THAT MAY NOT EMERGE FROM THE BROADER ASPECTS OF THE DESIGN.
> THE RISK OF IMAGE OVERPRODUCTION
IT IS EASY TO FALL INTO THE TRAP OF OVERPRODUCING IMAGES WHEN USING AI TOOLS, WHICH CAN LEAD TO INEFFICIENCY AND CREATIVE OVERLOAD. A MORE TARGETED APPROACH IS ESSENTIAL TO AVOID GENERATING AN EXCESSIVE NUMBER OF IRRELEVANT OR UNUSED IMAGES.

User personas

MATTEO

A.5.15

"I NEED A TOOL THAT LETS ME FREELY BROWSE THROUGH UNIQUE VISUALS, WITHOUT WORRYING ABOUT HOW TO PHRASE A PROMPT OR REFINE EVERY SINGLE DETAIL. I WANT TO BE INSPIRED, NOT BOGGED DOWN BY TECHNICALITIES."

- >AGE: 24
>BACKGROUND: MASTER'S STUDENT IN VISUAL COMMUNICATION
>DESIGN FOCUS: GRAPHIC DESIGN AND EDITORIAL DESIGN

> BEHAVIORAL PATTERN:
MATTEO IS PASSIONATE ABOUT DISCOVERING UNIQUE AND NICHE VISUAL CONTENT. HE OFTEN BROWSES PLATFORMS LIKE PINTEREST, SAVEE, ARENA AND CIFRA TO FIND UNCONVENTIONAL IMAGES AND STYLES THAT INSPIRE HIS WORK. MATTEO VALUES TOOLS THAT OFFER A SIMPLE AND INTUITIVE WAY TO EXPLORE AND COLLECT VISUALS, WITHOUT BEING LIMITED BY THE COMPLEXITY OF CRAFTING DETAILED PROMPTS OR STRUGGLING TO GET SPECIFIC OUTPUTS. MATTEO VALUES TOOLS THAT PROVIDE EASY ACCESS TO INTERESTING OUTPUTS, ESPECIALLY THOSE THAT ARE NOT COMMONLY FOUND ELSEWHERE.

> NEEDS AND GOALS:
MATTEO WANTS CONTENTS THAT ALLOWS HIM TO EXPLORE A DIVERSE RANGE OF GENERATIVE OUTPUTS WITHOUT NEEDED TO FOCUS ON PERFECTING PROMPTS OR GENERATING NEW CONTENT HIMSELF. HE SEEKS A TOOL THAT STREAMLINES HIS CREATIVE EXPLORATION, ENABLING HIM TO STUMBLE UPON VISUALLY INTERESTING IDEAS THAT HE CAN INTEGRATE INTO HIS PROJECTS.

> PAIN POINTS:
FINDS IT DIFFICULT TO TRANSLATE ABSTRACT IDEAS INTO TEXT-BASED PROMPTS.DISLIKES THE REPETITIVE AND PREDICTABLE OUTPUTS FROM MOST AI TOOLS.NEEDS MORE INTUITIVE WAYS TO MANIPULATE AND EXPLORE CONTENT.

BEHAVIOURAL CHARACTERISTICS:

- EXPLORATION AND CONTENT DISCOVERY: [Progress bar with 10 squares, 9 filled]
RELIANCE ON TEXT-BASED PROMPTS: [Progress bar with 10 squares, 3 filled]
INTEREST IN IMPERFECT OUTPUTS: [Progress bar with 10 squares, 8 filled]
USE OF AI FOR FINAL CONTENT CREATION: [Progress bar with 10 squares, 2 filled]
DESIRE FOR SERENDIPITOUS DISCOVERIES: [Progress bar with 10 squares, 9 filled]
NEED FOR VISUAL UNIQUENESS: [Progress bar with 10 squares, 10 filled]

ANNA

“I WANT TO FIND THE RIGHT VISUALS QUICKLY WITHOUT GENERATING A TON OF UNNECESSARY OUTPUTS. I KNOW SUSTAINABILITY IS IMPORTANT, BUT I DONT THINK DIGITAL DESIGN COULD CONTRIBUTE THAT BAD TO ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT.”

>AGE: 21
 >BACKGROUND: BACHELOR'S STUDENT IN DIGITAL MEDIA DESIGN
 >DESIGN FOCUS: UI/UX DESIGN AND MOTION GRAPHICS

> BEHAVIORAL PATTERN:
 ANNA USES GENERATIVE AI TOOLS FREQUENTLY TO CREATE IMAGES FOR HER PROJECTS, BUT SHE OFTEN GENERATES MANY OUTPUTS THAT SHE ENDS UP DISCARDING. WHILE SHE CONSIDERS HERSELF ENVIRONMENTALLY CONSCIOUS, SHE IS UNAWARE OF THE POTENTIAL DIGITAL WASTE GENERATED BY HER ACTIONS. ANNA WISHES SHE COULD FIND INTERESTING AND RELEVANT VISUALS MORE EASILY WITHOUT HAVING TO GENERATE NUMEROUS OPTIONS.

> NEEDS AND GOALS:
 ANNA NEEDS A TOOL THAT PROVIDES DIVERSE CONTENT OPTIONS TO INTEGRATE DIRECTLY INTO HER FINAL OUTPUTS, REDUCING THE NEED TO GENERATE NEW MATERIAL REPEATEDLY. AT THE SAME TIME, SHE WOULD BENEFIT FROM MORE INFORMATION ABOUT THE IMPACT OF HER USAGE AND TIPS ON SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES THAT DON'T DISRUPT HER CREATIVE FLOW.

> PAIN POINTS:
 UNINTENTIONALLY GENERATES A LOT OF UNNECESSARY OUTPUTS, LEADING TO CREATIVE OVERWHELM.STRUGGLING IN FINDING FREE RIGHTS CONTENTS TO IMPLEMENT IN HER PROJECTS LACK OF AWARENESS ON DIGITAL WASTE EVEN SHE IS ENVIRONMENTAL CONCIIOUS.

BEHAVIOURAL CHARACTERISTICS:

Conclusion

A.5.16

The survey and interviews provided valuable insights into how design students and professionals currently use and perceive Generative AI tools. While AI is primarily used for ideation and exploration, designers face challenges translating visual ideas into text-based prompts, leading to a high rate of discarded outputs. This not only impacts their creative workflow but also contributes to increased AI energy consumption. The findings reveal a strong interest in exploring and reusing imperfect AI outputs as sources of creative inspiration, highlighting the potential to redefine “generative waste” as a valuable design resource. Additionally, the lack of awareness regarding the environmental impact of AI usage presents an opportunity to integrate educational elements and sustainable practices into the design process. By addressing these gaps, a more sustainable and intuitive approach to using AI can be developed, enhancing both the creative possibilities and environmental responsibility of designers.

GenAI tools benchmark analysis

A.5.17

Through our discussions with designers, we identified two main categories of tools commonly used in the design process for inspiration and image generation:

> **Visual references platforms (e.g., Pinterest, Behance)**

> **Generative AI tools (e.g., MidJourney, DALL-E)**

To better understand the advantages and limitations of these tools, we conducted a benchmark analysis, which helped position our project within the current landscape. The analysis focused on two key factors:

> **Serendipity and Exploration Possibilities**

Designers consistently emphasized that one of the primary advantages of using AI tools is the serendipity in discovering unexpected results. This randomness enhances creative exploration and allows for innovative solutions. However, a significant challenge highlighted by designers is the difficulty in expressing their visual ideas through text-based prompts, as it is often hard to translate visual concepts into words. This constraint forces them to know what they are looking for before getting results, which can limit creative outcomes. On the other pole, traditional image exploration platforms like Pinterest or Behance, allow for serendipitous results with much more challenge. The interfaces are often limited to scrolling interactions, making it harder to stumble upon truly unexpected content. While these platforms provide inspiration, they lack the creative flexibility AI tools offer, and designers are left with only inspirational material, not usable outputs due to copyright restrictions.

Project Opportunities:

> The project aims to bridge this gap by repurposing AI-generated waste—the discarded, unexpected outputs that often have creative potential. By offering designers the ability to explore and re-use these outputs, we tap into the power of AI serendipity, allowing for greater creative freedom without the need to formulate precise prompts.

> **Sustainability and Efficiency**

The more powerful and time-efficient the tool, the higher the environmental cost. AI tools that generate complex outputs often consume large amounts of resources due to the intensive computational power required. While these tools are fast and convenient, they are not always aligned with sustainable design practices. On the other hand, platforms like Pinterest and Behance, while more sustainable due to their lower resource usage, do not allow designers to directly use the content. These platforms require a slower creative process, as designers need to reinterpret and recreate visuals they find due to copyright restrictions. Additionally, the environmental impact of these platforms depends on factors such as data storage, data center efficiency, and the amount of content being stored and processed.

Project Opportunities:

> Our project seeks to adopt a sustainable approach by repurposing generative waste—the outputs that would otherwise be discarded. By promoting the creative reuse of these materials, we aim to minimize unnecessary energy consumption from generating new outputs. Furthermore, we plan to raise awareness about digital waste and the environmental impact of AI tools by providing transparency on the data storage and energy costs associated with discarded content.

[FIG 11]

[FIG 12]

Conclusion

A.5.18

The insights gathered from our benchmark analysis and interviews show that designers need a tool that balances creativity, sustainability, and ease of exploration. By focusing on reusing generative outputs and offering a more intuitive exploration interface, our project not only addresses the environmental concerns associated with AI but also enhances creative freedom by leveraging the unexpected, serendipitous nature of AI-generated content.

How might we *repurpose* discarded AI-generated content to help design students *explore* unconventional outputs in a more *intuitive* and *serendipitous* way, while also raising *awareness* about the environmental impact of generative AI?

Gathering data

A.7.1

To better understand the potential of repurposing AI-generated content, a dataset was collected by inviting design students and practitioners to share their discarded generative outputs through a shared drive link. The accepted content types included images, videos, and 3D files—formats known for being among the most computationally intensive and power-hungry to generate using AI tools. While the project primarily focuses on images, due to the opportunity for testing with designers, this does not exclude the possibility that other types of discarded AI content, such as videos and 3D files, could also be valuable for repurposing in future iterations.

Reached datas:

- > images
- > videos
- > 3D files

[FIG 13]

[FIG 14]

[FIG 15]

[FIG 16]

[FIG 17]

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[FIG 267]

[FIG 268]

Workshop
A.8.1

TO ASSESS THE POTENTIAL BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES OF INCORPORATING “GENERATIVE WASTE” INTO THE DESIGN PROCESS, A WORKSHOP WAS ORGANIZED. THE AIM WAS TO EVALUATE HOW DESIGNERS CATEGORIZE DISCARDED AI-GENERATED IMAGES AND HOW THEY LEVERAGE THE UNIQUE CHARACTERISTICS OF THESE IMAGES TO DEVELOP VISUAL CONCEPTS. THIS HANDS-ON SESSION PROVIDED VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO HOW DESIGNERS INTERACT WITH GENERATIVE WASTE AND THE CREATIVE POSSIBILITIES IT OFFERS. THE PROJECT PRIMARILY FOCUSED ON VISUAL DESIGNERS, DUE TO THE ACCESSIBILITY PROVIDED BY THE UNIVERSITY. HOWEVER, THIS APPROACH COULD ALSO PROVE VALUABLE ACROSS OTHER DESIGN DISCIPLINES.

WORKSHOP PARTECIPANTS

- 11
 - 2 - EX VISUAL COMMUNICATION STUDENTS
 - 7 - VISUAL COMMUNICATIONS STUDENTS
 - 2 -EXTERNAL
 - > ANALYZED IMAGES
- 100
 - > WORKSHOP DURATION
- 2H30M

WORKSHOP OBJECTIVE

THE GOAL OF THIS WORKSHOP IS TO EXPLORE HOW AI-GENERATED IMAGES, OFTEN DISCARDED FOR BEING IMPERFECT OR UNSUITABLE, CAN BE REWORKED TO CREATE NEW VISUAL CONTENT. STUDENTS WILL BE ENCOURAGED TO VIEW “GENERATIVE WASTE” NOT AS USELESS MATERIAL, BUT AS CREATIVE RESOURCES FROM WHICH TO DRAW INSPIRATION.

WORKSHOP FINAL OUTPUT

A NARRATIVE POSTER (A3) IN DIGITAL FORMAT.

WORKSHOP SCHEDULE

IMAGE ANALYSIS AND TAGGING (20 IMAGES PER GROUP)
EACH GROUP EXAMINES THE PROVIDED IMAGES AND DISCUSSES HOW TO TAG THEM BASED ON CRITERIA THAT MAY INCLUDE, BUT ARE NOT LIMITED TO:

>VISUAL ASPECTS:

DOMINANT COLOR, TEXTURE, STYLE (ABSTRACT, REALISTIC, ETC.);

> CONTENT:

RECURRING SUBJECTS, EMOTIONS EVOKED, NARRATIVE CONTENT;

> OUTPUT QUALITY:

DEGREE OF DISTORTION, DEGREE OF DEFINITION, GENERATIVE ERRORS;

CLUSTERING:

STUDENTS GROUP IMAGES BASED ON THE IDENTIFIED CRITERIA AND TAGS OF ANALYSIS DEFINING DIFFERENT GROUPS OF IMAGES. THE CLUSTERS ARE THEN NAMED ON THE BASE OF THE VISUAL PATTERN OF THE IMAGES, THEMES OR EMOTIONS EVOKED.

THEME SELECTION (5 MINUTES):

EACH GROUP CHOOSES ONE OF THE DEFINED THEMATIC CLUSTERS. THE SELECTED CLUSTER SERVE AS A STARTING POINT FOR DEFINING THE CONCEPT OF THE NARRATIVE POSTER. STUDENTS DISCUSS WHICH ASPECT OF THE CLUSTER'S THEME THEY WANT TO EMPHASIZE: A POSITIVE MESSAGE, A CRITIQUE, AN IRONIC CONCEPT, ETC.

CONCEPT DEFINITION AND STORYTELLING:

GROUPS DEVELOP A NARRATIVE IDEA FOR THEIR POSTER BY:

> IMAGE SELECTION AND MANIPULATION:

EACH GROUP SELECTS THE IMAGES THAT BEST REPRESENT THEIR CHOSEN THEME AND REWORKS THEM GRAPHICALLY USING DESIGN SOFTWARE.

THEY CAN MAKE ADJUSTMENTS TO IMPROVE IMPERFECTIONS (E.G., COLOR CORRECTION, DEFECT REMOVAL) OR EMPHASIZE GENERATIVE ERRORS TO ACHIEVE INTERESTING AND UNEXPECTED VISUAL EFFECTS.

POSTER DESIGN:

STUDENTS DEFINE THE LAYOUT OF THE POSTER: HOW TO ARRANGE THE IMAGES, WHAT THE FOCAL POINT WILL BE, AND HOW TO HARMONIZE TEXT AND VISUALS.

EACH GROUP SHOULD CREATE A FINAL DIGITAL VERSION (A3 FORMAT)

SURVEY FOR FEEDBACK:

AT THE END OF THE WORKSHOP, PARTICIPANTS ARE INVITED TO COMPLETE A SURVEY TO PROVIDE FEEDBACK ON THEIR EXPERIENCE.

WORKSHOP FEEDBACKS

THE SURVEY FOCUSED ON THE PARTICIPANTS' EXPERIENCES WITH GENERATIVE WASTE DURING A CREATIVE PROCESS. THE RESULTS INDICATE AN OVERALL POSITIVE RECEPTION, WITH SOME SPECIFIC HIGHLIGHTS AND AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT:

USEFULNESS OF IMPERFECT GENERATIVE WASTE:

MOST PARTICIPANTS RATED THE GENERATIVE WASTE HIGHLY, WITH SCORES PREDOMINANTLY IN THE 4-5 RANGE ON A SCALE OF 5. THIS SUGGESTS THAT THE GENERATIVE MATERIALS WERE CONSIDERED VALUABLE DURING THE CREATIVE PHASE.

UNLOCKING NEW IDEAS OR PERSPECTIVES:

THE MAJORITY OF PARTICIPANTS (ALSO RATED 4-5) INDICATED THAT THE GENERATIVE WASTE HELPED THEM UNLOCK FRESH IDEAS OR NEW PERSPECTIVES, CONTRIBUTING POSITIVELY TO THEIR CREATIVE WORK.

POTENTIAL FOR FUTURE USE:

THE RESPONSES REVEALED A STRONG BELIEF IN THE POTENTIAL OF THESE MATERIALS FOR FUTURE PROJECTS. PARTICIPANTS MOSTLY RESPONDED "YES" OR "IN PART," SUGGESTING THEY SEE EITHER FULL OR PARTIAL APPLICABILITY OF GENERATIVE WASTE IN THEIR ONGOING OR FUTURE WORK.

MOST USEFUL CHARACTERISTICS:

- >PARTICIPANTS FOUND THE FOLLOWING ASPECTS PARTICULARLY USEFUL:
- >FRESH PERSPECTIVES IN INTERPRETING CREATIVE CONCEPTS;
- >THE ABILITY TO UTILIZE GRAPHIC DISTORTIONS AND IMPERFECTIONS CREATIVELY;
- >THE VARIETY AND QUALITY OF THE IMAGES; AMBIGUOUS SHAPES AND TEXTURES THAT INSPIRED NEW IDEAS.

LEAST USEFUL OR PROBLEMATIC ASPECTS:

A FEW PARTICIPANTS MENTIONED TECHNICAL ISSUES SUCH AS THE POOR QUALITY OF SOME IMAGES AND UNCLEAR SUBJECTS. HOWEVER, SOME RESPONDENTS EMPHASIZED THAT THERE WERE NO REAL ISSUES, WITH ONE PARTICIPANT STATING, "NOTHING, EVERYTHING HAS VALUE."

USEFULNESS OF IMAGE LABELING:

MOST PARTICIPANTS FOUND THE LABELING OF IMAGES HELPFUL FOR SPARKING PROJECT IDEAS, WITH SEVERAL INDICATING IT WAS AT LEAST PARTIALLY USEFUL.

OVERALL IMPRESSION:

THE SURVEY REVEALS THAT GENERATIVE WASTE WAS GENERALLY WELL-RECEIVED, AIDING CREATIVITY AND IDEA GENERATION. THE PARTICIPANTS ACKNOWLEDGED THE POTENTIAL OF THESE MATERIALS IN FUTURE WORK WHILE NOTING SOME TECHNICAL SHORTCOMINGS THAT COULD BE IMPROVED. THE SURVEY HIGHLIGHTS THE CREATIVE VALUE OF IMPERFECTIONS AND VARIETY IN GENERATIVE WASTE MATERIALS.

[FIG 269]

[FIG 270]

[FIG 271]

[FIG 272]

[FIG 273]

Insights summary

A.9.1

Sustainability needs:

The environmental impact of GenAI is a pressing issue, and as individuals, it's challenging to address the problem at its root. Therefore, the project must focus on how the public uses these AI models to implement digital sustainability practices. Digital realism urgently needs to adopt better sustainable strategies that encourage individuals to take a more mindful approach. Although some initiatives have been introduced to raise awareness about the ecological footprint of digital actions, the issue—particularly in terms of GenAI consumption—has not been effectively communicated to the public.

When discussing applied digital sustainability practices, case studies like “Ddump” and “The Digital Upcycling Project” illustrate that efforts such as recycling digital materials often serve speculative or artistic purposes. This highlights the lack of accessible services that can help people grasp the problem more fully and inspire action, such as BitShrinking while also providing individuals with access to digital waste materials, especially generative waste, empowering them to Curate, Rethink, and Recode it.

Design students needs:

The insights gathered from our benchmark analysis and interviews show that designers need a tool that balances creativity, sustainability, and ease of exploration. By focusing on reusing generative outputs and offering a more intuitive exploration interface, our project not only addresses the environmental concerns associated with AI but also enhances creative freedom by leveraging the unexpected, serendipitous nature of AI-generated content.

Generative Waste validation:

The workshop demonstrated the significant creative potential of generative waste, with participants embracing imperfections and unexpected results as valuable resources for ideation. The overall feedback was highly positive, with most participants finding the discarded AI-generated images useful for unlocking fresh ideas and exploring new perspectives. The process of categorizing, reworking, and repurposing the images helped students recognize the unique value of “imperfect” outputs, leading to innovative visual concepts. While some technical issues, such as image quality, were noted,

the majority of participants expressed strong confidence in the future applicability of generative waste in their design projects. The workshop reinforced the importance of creative reuse, highlighting how discarded materials can inspire meaningful design, and emphasized the need for more intuitive exploration and categorization tools to further enhance the creative process.

Concept definition

A.10.1

The project aims to develop an interactive interface for design students, particularly those focused on visual design, that promotes sustainable digital practices to reduce the environmental impact of using generative AI. The platform will specifically focus on AI-generated image waste and will:

- > Offer a “curated” collection of “generative waste” content for students to explore, “rethink”, and draw inspiration from.
- > Educate students about the environmental impact of generative AI, raising awareness about digital resource consumption.
- > Provide an intuitive interface that supports serendipitous exploration of discarded AI-generated materials.
- > Enable students to “recode” generative waste, transforming it into valuable content for their visual projects.
- > Allow students to donate their own generative waste, enabling them to share discarded outputs with others and contribute to the creative community.
- > Apply sustainable practices to optimize the platform consumptions.

This interface promotes creative reuse, fosters sustainability, and empowers students to adopt a more environmentally conscious approach to design by reducing digital waste. The project envisions “BitShrinking” generative waste by offering valuable sources of inspiration and Creative Commons content.

It leverages recent studies on the creative potential of AI-generated content, focusing on a key insight from the research: imperfect outputs often spark more creativity than flawless ones. The goal is to support designers explore and experiment with unconventional and unexpected outputs, turning discarded content into a powerful resource for inspiration and

innovation. Furthermore, the project envisions integrating the platform and the concept of “generative waste” into educational settings. This would allow design students and educators to incorporate sustainable practices into the curriculum, using generative waste as a tool for creative exploration and learning.

note:
The project focuses on the application and use of generative waste in visual design, as the research was conducted within a university environment where data availability was influenced by this context. However, this does not exclude the possibility that the project could be explored and applied in other design fields as well, offering potential for broader applications across various disciplines.

Legenda:

> BitShrink: Focused on minimizing the amount of data and digital resources by compressing information, optimizing storage, and reducing digital waste. This term conveys the idea of shrinking data footprints and cutting down on unnecessary bits in digital processes.

> Rethink: This term conveys the idea of taking existing digital assets, and adapting or modifying them for new uses. It involves using creative thinking to adapt what already exists for a different purpose, without major structural changes.

> Recode: Transforming outdated or redundant digital materials through restructuring or reprogramming to reintegrate them into the digital ecosystem. Emphasizes the technical transformation of outdated or redundant digital materials.

> Curate: Organizing and managing digital content and data, ensuring proper categorization and archiving to streamline future usage and reduce digital clutter.

Slow design

A.10.2

The project aims to position itself within the education field by adopting Slow Design Principles alongside remapped digital sustainable methodologies—BitShrink, ReThink, and ReCode—to foster sustainable design behavior among students. Slow Design Principles, as outlined in the literature, emphasize reflection, adaptability, and personal interpretation, encouraging designers to continuously question and refine their work. This iterative process often leads to shifting briefs and evolving outcomes, enabling deeper exploration of the designer’s identity, role, and the broader impact of their creations. [28] Strauss, C. F., & Fuad-Luke, A. F.-L. (2008)

Reveal:
Bringing attention to the often unnoticed experiences, materials, and processes that define everyday life. (Strauss and [28] Strauss, C. F., & Fuad-Luke, A. F.-L. (2008)

Expand:
Exploring possibilities that go beyond the assumed functions and lifespans of a given environment. [28] Strauss, C. F., & Fuad-Luke, A. F.-L. (2008)

Reflect:
Designing spaces that encourage thoughtfulness, self-awareness, and contemplation. [28] Strauss, C. F., & Fuad-Luke, A. F.-L. (2008)

Engage:
Promoting collaboration and openness through shared resources, cooperation, and transparent information, enabling designs to adapt and grow over time. [28] Strauss, C. F., & Fuad-Luke, A. F.-L. (2008)

Participate:
Motivating individuals to actively contribute to the design process by incorporating local insights and addressing user needs. [28] Strauss, C. F., & Fuad-Luke, A. F.-L. (2008)

Evolve:
Emphasizing the value of dynamic growth, where deeper experiences emerge as artifacts and environments develop over time. [28] Strauss, C. F., & Fuad-Luke, A. F.-L. (2008)

onliness statement

A.10.3

“The only educational framework that empowers students and educators to foster a more sustainable use of generative AI by providing an interactive digital environment to access ‘generative waste’ content thanks to an open-source system that enables the creation of micro-servers within schools. This system allows the donation of discarded generative AI content, giving it new life. In an era where promoting the principles of slow design can be crucial for fostering awareness on sustainable design practices.”

As is journey

A.10.4

THE JOURNEY MAPS HIGHLIGHT THE DISTINCT EXPERIENCES AND CHALLENGES FACED BY THE TWO PERSONAS, MATTEO AND ANNA, EMPHASIZING THEIR UNIQUE INTERACTIONS AND PAIN POINTS WITHIN THE DESIGN PROCESS.

MATTEO’S JOURNEY

PAIN POINTS:

- > DIFFICULTY IN FINDING UNIQUE AND UNCONVENTIONAL VISUALS ON TRADITIONAL PLATFORMS.
- > STRUGGLES WITH THE COMPLEXITY OF TEXT-BASED PROMPTS AND SERENDIPITOUS EXPLORATION.
- > THE PROCESS TO REFINE PROMPTS AND GENERATE SATISFACTORY RESULTS IS TIME-CONSUMING.

OPPORTUNITIES:

- > FACILITATING EXPLORATION OF UNCONVENTIONAL CONTENT AND PLATFORMS.
- > ENCOURAGING SERENDIPITOUS DISCOVERY AND REDUCING REDUNDANT IMAGE GENERATION.
- > USING TAGS TO BETTER ORGANIZE AND ACCESS VISUAL CONTENT.
- > PROVIDING PRE-EXISTING PROMPTS FOR ALREADY GENERATED IMAGES TO GUIDE USERS IN CRAFTING MORE EFFECTIVE PROMPTS, THEREBY IMPROVING RESULTS, ENHANCING EFFICIENCY, AND MINIMIZING CREATIVE AND RESOURCE WASTE.

ANNA’S JOURNEY

PAIN POINTS:

- > HIGH DISCARD RATE FOR AI-GENERATED OUTPUTS DUE TO IRRELEVANCE OR QUALITY ISSUES.
- > LACK OF AWARENESS ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF GENERATIVE TOOLS.

OPPORTUNITIES:

- > EMPOWERING ANNA TO DONATE OR SHARE DISCARDED CONTENT WITH PEERS.
- > REDUCING WASTE BY IMPROVING ACCESS TO PREVIOUSLY GENERATED CONTENT.
- > EDUCATING USERS ON THE ECOLOGICAL FOOTPRINT OF AI TOOLS.

As is journey

MATTEO	PROJECT BRIEF	IDEATION	
ACTIONS	Receives project brief from the teacher	Starts gathering ideas by sketching.	Starts browsing platforms for visual inspo
PAIN POINTS		<p>Difficulty in finding niche unique visuals on traditional platforms</p> <p>Difficulty in exploring platform contents and get unexpected inspiration</p>	
WIN POINTS		Finds some initial inspiration	After a lot of research finds some visual inspo
OPPORTUNITIES		<p>Facilitate the research of unconventional outputs</p> <p>Improvements for a more serendipitous exploration</p>	

CONCEPT Development	VISUAL EXPLORATION	VISUAL EXPERIMENTATION	FINAL DESIGN
Create a moodboard with some visual inspo	Starts to use midjourney to get some interesting visual results	Refines and adjusts selected AI-generated visuals in photoshop to fit the project aesthetics	Delivers the final design
Limited open source visual and unconventional contents free to use	<p>Struggling with the complexity of creating text-based prompts that accurately translate his visual ideas</p> <p>The process to refine prompting to get meaningful results is long and Matteo generates a lot of outputs that he would not actually use</p>	Wishes for more unexpected and unconventional visual material to work with	Feel frustrated and doesn't feel completely satisfied by the final output
	Gets some interesting visual results	Finds success in improving and reworking visual outputs, adding a personal touch to the AI-generated content	
Promote an open-source approach for sharing not used content between design students	<p>Reduce the image generation giving access to already generated contents</p> <p>Improvements for prompting formulation and optimization</p>	Taking advantages of unusual outputs and AI errors from generative waste	

As is journey

ANNA	PROJECT BRIEF	IDEATION
ACTIONS	Receives project brief from the teacher	Starts to generate visual-content for inspiration
PAIN POINTS		<p>Many generated contents are discarded due to a lack of quality or irrelevance</p> <p>Unawareness of GenAI consumption</p>
WIN POINTS		Gets some interesting visual results
OPPORTUNITIES		<p>Empower to donate to other students not used generated contents</p> <p>Reduce the image generation giving access to already generated contents</p>

CONCEPT Development	VISUAL EXPLORATION	VISUAL EXPERIMENTATION	FINAL DESIGN
Create a moodboard with AI-generated visual images	Uses AI tools to refine her visual content exploring different iterations	Select her final AI-generated visuals and begins refining them on photoshop	Delivers the final design
	Unawareness of GenAI consumption		
		Successfully refines the visuals she's satisfied with and makes progress on her final design	
	Raise awareness on the environmental impact of GenAI		

Key features

A.10.5

TO ADDRESS THE IDENTIFIED PAIN POINTS AND CAPITALIZE ON THE OPPORTUNITIES, KEY FEATURES HAVE BEEN DEVELOPED TO MEET THE NEEDS OF DESIGN STUDENTS AND PROMOTE SUSTAINABILITY WITHIN THE PROJECT FRAMEWORK. THE FEATURES ARE CAREFULLY DESIGNED TO ADDRESS BOTH USER AND SUSTAINABILITY NEEDS, ENSURING A BALANCE BETWEEN FUNCTIONALITY, CREATIVITY, AND ECOLOGICAL RESPONSIBILITY.

DESIGN STUDENTS NEEDS

UNIQUE AND UNEXPECTED VISUAL CONTENT

- > FEATURE: AN AGGREGATOR FOR UNCONVENTIONAL GENAI OUTPUTS, PROVIDING ACCESS TO VISUALLY DISTINCT AND SURPRISING CONTENT.
- > REVEAL – THIS FEATURE BRINGS ATTENTION TO OVERLOOKED OR UNCONVENTIONAL AI-GENERATED OUTPUTS, UNCOVERING HIDDEN POSSIBILITIES WITHIN DISCARDED MATERIALS.

OPEN-SOURCE OR FREE-TO-USE CONTENT

- > FEATURE: A “THROW AWAY YOUR GENAI WASTE” SYSTEM THAT COLLECTS DISCARDED AI-GENERATED OUTPUTS AND MAKES THEM FREELY ACCESSIBLE FOR REUSE.
- > ENGAGE – ENCOURAGES OPENNESS AND SHARING WITHIN THE DESIGN COMMUNITY BY MAKING DISCARDED OUTPUTS ACCESSIBLE.
- > PARTICIPATE – MOTIVATES USERS TO ACTIVELY CONTRIBUTE TO A SHARED RESOURCE, FOSTERING COLLABORATION AND INCLUSION.

ENGAGING AND SERENDIPITOUS EXPLORATION OF CONTENT

- > FEATURE: A GENEROUS INTERFACE DESIGNED TO FACILITATE EXPLORATION WITHOUT REQUIRING USERS TO KNOW EXACTLY WHAT THEY’RE SEARCHING FOR, FOSTERING CREATIVE DISCOVERY.
- > EXPAND – SUPPORTS THE EXPLORATION OF UNEXPECTED POSSIBILITIES BEYOND INITIAL ASSUMPTIONS OR INTENDED USES.
- > REFLECT – ENCOURAGES USERS TO PAUSE AND CONTEMPLATE THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN CONTENT, FOSTERING MEANINGFUL EXPLORATION.

SIMPLIFIED TRANSLATION OF VISUAL CONCEPTS INTO TEXT PROMPTS

- > FEATURE: ACCESS TO FREE-TO-USE GENAI CONTENT WITH THE OPTION TO VIEW AND USE ASSOCIATED PROMPTS, ENABLING USERS TO REFINE AND ITERATE MORE EFFICIENTLY IF NEEDED.
- > ENGAGE – PROMOTES TRANSPARENCY BY PROVIDING PROMPTS THAT HELP USERS BETTER UNDERSTAND AND REFINE THE GENERATIVE PROCESS.
- > REFLECT – FACILITATES THOUGHTFUL ITERATION, ENABLING USERS TO ALIGN OUTPUTS WITH THEIR CREATIVE INTENTIONS.

SUSTAINABILITY NEEDS

REDUCE RESOURCE-INTENSIVE CONTENT GENERATION

- > FEATURE: FREE ACCESS TO GENERATIVE “WASTE” AND DIDACTIC RESOURCES, ENCOURAGING CREATIVE REUSE OF DISCARDED OUTPUTS AND REDUCING COMPUTATIONAL DEMANDS.
- > REVEAL – HIGHLIGHTS THE POTENTIAL OF OVERLOOKED AND DISCARDED GENERATIVE OUTPUTS.
- > EVOLVE – ENCOURAGES DYNAMIC REUSE, ENABLING DISCARDED MATERIALS TO TAKE ON NEW FORMS AND MEANINGS.

MINIMIZE BIG DATA STORAGE

- > FEATURES:
 - > SMALL, OPEN-SOURCE LOCAL SERVERS FOR EACH SCHOOL TO STORE AND PERIODICALLY CLEAN OUTDATED DATA.
 - > A SUSTAINABLE INTERFACE WITH IMAGE COMPRESSION TECHNIQUES TO LOWER ENERGY CONSUMPTION.
 - > APPLICATION OF SLOW DESIGN PRINCIPLES, ENCOURAGING ACTIVE PARTICIPATION IN TAGGING IMAGES MANUALLY TO MINIMIZE THE USE OF COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES.
- > PARTICIPATE – INVITES USERS TO ACTIVELY CONTRIBUTE BY TAGGING CONTENT, CREATING A SHARED AND EFFICIENT SYSTEM.
- > REFLECT – PROMOTES MINDFUL INTERACTION WITH CONTENT ORGANIZATION PROCESSES.

PROMOTE RESPONSIBLE GENAI CONSUMPTION

- > FEATURE: A SYSTEM THAT MAPS AND VISUALIZES THE RESOURCE CONSUMPTION ASSOCIATED WITH DISCARDED CONTENT, RAISING AWARENESS AND ENCOURAGING MORE THOUGHTFUL USER BEHAVIOR.
- > REFLECT – ENCOURAGES SELF-AWARENESS AND INTROSPECTION ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF RESOURCE CONSUMPTION.
- > ENGAGE – INVOLVES USERS IN UNDERSTANDING AND ADDRESSING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF THEIR CREATIVE PRACTICES.

Features

DESIGN STUDENTS NEEDS

UNIQUE AND UNEXPECTED VISUAL CONTENTS

OPEN-SOURCE OR FREE TO USE CONTENTS

ENGAGING AND SERENDIPITOUS EXPLORATION OF CONTENTS

SIMPLIFIED TRANSLATION OF VISUAL CONCEPTS INTO TEXT PROMPTS

FEATURES

Unconvenient GenAI outputs aggregator

Throw away your GenAI waste feature and free access/use of discarded contents

Generous interface that allow to explore contents without necessarily know what you are looking for

Access to free-to-use GenAI content with the option to view and use associated prompts, enabling users to refine and iterate more efficiently if needed.

SUSTAINABILITY NEEDS

REDUCE COMPUTATIONAL HUNGRY CONTENTS GENERATION

REDUCE BIG DATA STORAGE

ADDRESS GEN AI CONSUMPTION WITH A MORE AWARED SELF BEHAVIOUR

FEATURES

Free access to generative waste and didactic sources in order to creatively re-use them

Small open source local servers to store and clean out dated data

Sustainable interface and image compression in order to reduce consumes

Slow design principles of active participation to self tag images in order to avoid computational resources

Mapping and showing discarded contents consumes

To be journey

MATTEO	PROJECT BRIEF		IDEATION		CONCEPT Development	VISUAL EXPLORATION	VISUAL EXPERIMENTATION	FINAL DESIGN
ACTIONS	Teacher provide students an introductory workshop that take advantage of discarded GenAI contents to develop a visual concept	Receives project briefs from the teacher	Starts gathering ideas by sketching	Start explore the GenAI waste contents on the platform	Create a moodboard with some GenAI waste visual inspo	Gets interesting contents to manipulate from GenAI waste platform	Refines and adjusts selected visuals in photoshop to fit the project aesthetic Refines and adjusts selected visuals using suggested prompts in a GenAI tool effectively	Delivers the final design
FEATURES	Free access to generative waste and didactic sources in order to creatively re-use them			Unconvenient GenAI outputs aggregator Generous interface that allow to explore contents without necessarily know what you are looking for	Thorw away your GenAI waste feature and free access/use of discarded contents Access to free-to-use GenAI content with the option to view and use associated prompts, enabling users to refine and iterate more efficiently if needed.			
ANNA	PROJECT BRIEF		IDEATION		CONCEPT Development	VISUAL EXPLORATION	VISUAL EXPERIMENTATION	FINAL DESIGN
ACTIONS	Receives project brief from the teacher		Starts to generate visual content for inspiration		Drops her extra contents in the GenAI waste platform	Uses the platform to find some useful content for the project	Selects the final contents and refine them on photoshop	Delivers the final design
FEATURES	Thorw away your GenAI waste feature and free access/use of discarded contents Small open source local servers to store and clean out dated data			Mapping and showing discarded contents consumes Slow design principles of active participation to self tag images in order to avoid computational resources				

MATTEO'S JOURNEY

KEY IMPROVEMENTS:

> INTRODUCTION OF A WORKSHOP: MATTEO BENEFITS FROM AN INTRODUCTORY WORKSHOP THAT FOCUSES ON CREATIVELY REPURPOSING GENERATIVE AI WASTE, FOSTERING A DEEPER UNDERSTANDING OF HOW TO WORK WITH UNCONVENTIONAL OUTPUTS.

> ACCESS TO GENAI WASTE PLATFORMS: BY BROWSING THESE PLATFORMS, MATTEO GAINS ACCESS TO UNIQUE AND UNEXPECTED VISUAL INSPIRATION, REDUCING HIS STRUGGLE WITH FINDING UNCONVENTIONAL CONTENT.

> SUGGESTED PROMPTS: MATTEO NOW RECEIVES SUGGESTED PROMPTS ALONGSIDE THE VISUAL CONTENT, SIMPLIFYING HIS TEXT-TO-IMAGE TRANSLATION PROCESS AND ENABLING BETTER REFINEMENT OF HIS IDEAS.

OUTCOME:

MATTEO'S JOURNEY BECOMES MORE EFFICIENT AND SATISFYING. HE NO LONGER FEELS FRUSTRATED OR DISSATISFIED WITH THE FINAL DESIGN, AS THE PROVIDED TOOLS AND RESOURCES SUPPORT HIS CREATIVE PROCESS AND IMPROVE HIS OUTCOMES.

ANNA'S JOURNEY

KEY IMPROVEMENTS:

>USE OF A GENAI WASTE PLATFORM: ANNA DEPOSITS HER DISCARDED GENERATIVE OUTPUTS INTO THE PLATFORM, WHICH NOT ONLY PROMOTES REUSE BUT ALSO PROVIDES HER WITH ACCESS TO OTHERS' DISCARDED CONTENT, ENABLING A RICHER POOL OF INSPIRATION.

MAPPING CONSUMPTION: THE INCLUSION OF A FEATURE THAT VISUALIZES THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DISCARDED CONTENT HELPS ANNA BECOME MORE MINDFUL OF HER CONSUMPTION AND PROMOTES SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES.

> LOCAL SERVERS AND TAGGING SYSTEMS: SUSTAINABLE STORAGE SOLUTIONS AND MANUAL TAGGING PRACTICES MINIMIZE UNNECESSARY COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES WHILE HELPING ANNA ORGANIZE AND ACCESS CONTENT EFFECTIVELY.

OUTCOME:

ANNA'S JOURNEY BECOMES MORE SUSTAINABLE AND ORGANIZED. SHE GAINS BETTER-QUALITY VISUAL INSPIRATION WHILE ACTIVELY CONTRIBUTING TO REDUCING WASTE, ALIGNING HER CREATIVE PROCESS WITH ECOLOGICAL RESPONSIBILITY.

Touch points

A.10.7

With design students at the center, this scheme of touchpoints illustrates how their experience will be enhanced through three critical areas of focus. It demonstrates how the surrounding touchpoints will either be enhanced or replaced as part of the project:

Teacher:

The teacher's role is to enrich the learning process by introducing workshops, tools, and methodologies that promote sustainable and innovative design practices.

Institution Environment:

This encompasses the institution's infrastructure, resources, and policies, creating an enhanced environment that fosters exploration, collaboration, and sustainability.

GenAI Tools and Image Platforms:

This touchpoint will be partially replaced by the introduction of GenAI waste exploration platforms, allowing students to creatively repurpose discarded content while minimizing resource-intensive processes.

[FIG 274]

Generous interfaces

A.10.8

Generous interfaces offer a more engaging and exploratory alternative to traditional text-based search platforms by revealing the scale, richness, and complexity of digital collections. Unlike search interfaces, which demand specific queries and often withhold broader context, generous interfaces provide multiple entry points, enabling users to browse, discover, and interpret content intuitively. Instead of demanding a query, they support exploration alongside focused inquiry, revealing relationships and structures within a collection to enrich interpretation [29] Whitelaw, M. (2015). This approach creates greater engagement with audiences and goes far beyond the still-dominant search interfaces most collection websites rely on, providing next-generation, data-driven alternatives for visualizing and interacting with collections. [30] Schema Design. (2019, June 2)

The project aims to incorporate generous interfaces as a key feature to address the limitations of text-based search and prompt-driven platforms in visual content exploration. By leveraging the principles of generous interfaces, the project seeks to create an intuitive, browsable system that enables users to engage with visual content in a more serendipitous and exploratory way. This approach eliminates the need for users to translate their creative concepts into text-based prompts, offering multiple pathways to discover and connect with content that aligns with their ideas. By revealing the scale, relationships, and richness of available generative AI outputs, the project not only facilitates visual research but also promotes a more inclusive and accessible experience, allowing users to fully harness the potential of discarded and unconventional generative materials.

A comprehensive taxonomy of various case studies on generous interfaces has been developed, grounded in key analytical characteristics to better understand their design and functionality. The taxonomy focuses on the following dimensions:

> **Navigation Systems:**

This dimension explores how these interfaces facilitate interaction between the user and the content. It examines mechanisms such as panning, zooming, scrolling, and other interactive techniques to evaluate their effectiveness in guiding user engagement.

> **Environment:**

This criterion evaluates the spatial approach of the interface, comparing 2D and 3D environments to determine which provides a more intuitive and effective user experience. This analysis helps identify the advantages and challenges of each approach within the context of the platform's objectives.

> **Navigation Hierarchy:**

The hierarchical structure of navigation is analyzed to assess the levels of complexity users face when accessing detailed information. This includes understanding how intuitive or layered the information architecture is, ensuring it supports seamless exploration.

> **Content Display:**

This characteristic focuses on the various methods of presenting content visually. It compares conventional layouts, such as grids and lists, with more experimental and innovative approaches, such as graphs, timelines, and scatterplots, to understand their impact on user experience and content comprehension.

> **Information Seeking:**

This dimension investigates the different strategies for searching and retrieving information within the interface. It evaluates features like search bars, filters, categories, and serendipitous discovery mechanisms to understand how effectively users can locate desired content.

The analysis of the taxonomy provided valuable insights that helped identify the key characteristics necessary to structure the interface's interactions effectively. These characteristics were carefully selected to align with the goals of the platform, ensuring an intuitive and engaging user experience. The primary drivers chosen from the taxonomy are as follows:

> **Interactive Navigation:**

The use of panning, zooming, and dragging functionalities will be prioritized to enable fluid and dynamic interaction with the content, making the exploration process more engaging and intuitive.

> **3D Environment:**

A three-dimensional environment will be selected to enhance spatial awareness and provide a more immersive experience, allowing users to visualize and interact with content in a compelling way.

> **Simplified Navigation Hierarchy:**

A shallow navigation structure will be adopted to ensure that information remains immediately accessible, minimizing the cognitive load on users and enabling quick access to key content.

> **Innovative Content Display:**

Diverse content visualization methods, such as graphs and clusters, will be incorporated to facilitate user discovery and understanding. These formats are designed to present information in an organized yet visually rich manner, making content easier to find and interpret.

> **Filtering and Information Seeking:**

Advanced filtering mechanisms will be implemented to allow users to refine their searches and access multiple levels of information seamlessly. This approach supports both broad exploration and targeted inquiries, accommodating various user needs.

NAME	NAVIGATION SYSTEM:					ENVIRONMENT:		NAVIGATION HYERARCHY:			CONTENT DISPLAY:						INFORMATION SEEKING:		
	VERTICAL SCROLL	PANNING	ZOOMING	DRAG	WALK	2D	3D	DEEP	SUPERFICIAL	GRID	LIST	GRAPH	CLUSTER	TIMELINE	CHART	NETWORK	TAGS	SEARCH-BAR	TIME
Center for Australian art - Australian print + Printmaking	●					●		●		●	●						●		●
SOOTWORLD		●	●				●		●			●	●					●	
Early Modern Women's Complaint Poetry	●					●		●		●	●						●		
LCFMA21				●			●		●	●									
LCF SMC MA + BA 2021		●	●	●			●		●			●					●		
nextimage					●		●		●										
Mapping Chinese Art, 1972-2012	●						●		●	●				●					●
Simmonds Ltd	●					●			●	●							●		
Design at the FHP		●	●			●			●			●					●		
PixPlot		●	●				●		●			●	●						
hetnieuweinstituut	●					●			●				●				●		

Sustainable practices

Colors:

Research highlights that integrating sustainable strategies into interface design can significantly reduce resource consumption. For instance, the choice of a UI color palette plays a crucial role in lowering carbon emissions. According to Claire Knights (2022), darker colors like black are the least resource-intensive, followed by red and green, while lighter colors such as blue and white are among the most power-hungry options. [31] Knights, C. (2022, September 27) By carefully selecting energy-efficient colors, the project can not only be visually appealing but also environmentally responsible.

Image loading:

Given that the project is designed to manage a large volume of images, and loading pixels on a web page can be resource-intensive [32] Mightybytes. (2013, April 19), implementing an effective optimization strategy is essential. One key approach is lazy loading, which significantly reduces power consumption by loading images only when they are needed, such as when they come into the user's viewport. This method not only enhances the interface's sustainability but also improves performance by minimizing unnecessary data transfer and resource usage.

[FIG 275]

B.

PROJECT

Naming

B.1.1

To develop the project's branding, the focus centers on key concepts identified during the research, including:

Consumes-Waste-Education-Recycle-Sustainability-Digital-Visual-Images-GenerativeAI-Awareness-Bit-Storage-Generation-Students-Slow Design

From these, three foundational terms were selected to conceptually embody the core values that the project aims to promote:

> **Slow Design:**

Highlighting sustainable and reflective design practices.

> **Memoizing:**

Borrowed from programming, this optimization practice symbolizes resource efficiency and creative reuse.

> **Slow Motion:**

A metaphorical representation of the deliberate deceleration the project encourages, fostering mindfulness and intentionality.

The result of combining these three concepts is SLOMO, a name that encapsulates the project's essence and mission.

**SLOW DESIGN
MEMOIZING
SLOW MOTION**

SLOMO

SLOMO represents an harmonious blend of Slow Design, emphasizing sustainability and intentionality, Memoizing, symbolizing efficiency and creative reuse, and Slow Motion, suggesting a thoughtful deceleration in how we consume, create, and engage with digital resources.

Through its branding and philosophy, SLOMO promotes a new paradigm for design education, where students and educators are encouraged to pause, reflect, and repurpose. The name serves as both a reminder and an invitation to embrace a slower, more mindful approach to generative content and design, fostering creativity that is conscious of its impact on the digital realm.

Logo

B.1.2

THE SLOMO LOGO IS DESIGNED WITH PREDOMINANTLY SQUARE-BASED SHAPES TO EVOKE THE ESSENCE OF THE DIGITAL WORLD, REFERENCING BITS AND PIXELS AS FOUNDATIONAL ELEMENTS OF TECHNOLOGY. THE SUBTLE ADDITION OF ROUNDED EDGES SOFTENS THE GEOMETRIC STRUCTURE, CREATING A VISUAL METAPHOR FOR THE PROJECT'S ETHOS: A DELIBERATE SLOWING DOWN, BLENDING DIGITAL PRECISION WITH A SENSE OF MINDFULNESS.

LOGO CONTRUCTION

BLACK LOGO

WHITE LOGO

BRAND IN MOTION

THE SLOMO BRAND IS INTENTIONALLY DESIGNED TO DYNAMICALLY ADAPT ITS SHAPE AND LAYOUT BASED ON THE WIDTH OF THE MEDIA IT APPEARS ON. THIS ADAPTABILITY EMPHASIZES FLEXIBILITY AND RESPONSIVENESS WHILE MAINTAINING THE BRAND'S CORE IDENTITY. THE INTEGRATION OF SLOW-MOTION MOVEMENTS AS A DEFINING CHARACTERISTIC ENHANCES THE BRAND'S CONNECTION TO ITS CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATION THIS SLOW-MOTION BEHAVIOR IS NOT ONLY A VISUAL ELEMENT BUT ALSO AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE USER EXPERIENCE, INFLUENCING INTERFACE ANIMATIONS AND INTERACTIONS. THROUGH THESE FLUID TRANSITIONS, SLOMO COMMUNICATES ITS ETHOS OF DELIBERATE DESIGN AND SUSTAINABILITY, CREATING A COHESIVE AND ENGAGING EXPERIENCE ACROSS ALL PLATFORMS.

LOGO EXPANTION

SHORT LOGO

VISUAL ASSETS

Font

B.1.3

TWK LUSANNE
400

WEIGHT 400

TWK LUSANNE
700

WEIGHT 700

The big brown
fox jumps over
the lazy dog

SLOW
 DESIGN
 BIG IMPACT

SLOWMOTO

GLITCH
 IS THE NEW
 BLACK

SLOWMOTO

Image tagging tool

B.2.1

To enhance the workshop framework and introduce a method for self-tagging images to deconstruct their information, an image tagging tool has been developed. This tool aims to ignite creativity and foster a deeper understanding of image informations. By allowing participants to dissect and label images, the tool not only facilitates hands-on experimentation within workshops but also plays a critical role in gathering data to support the development of a data-driven platform. This dual-purpose approach enables both the testing of the educational framework and the collection of valuable insights to inform and refine the platform's structure.

PROTOTYPES

LOW-FI

[FIG 276]

WIREFRAME

[FIG 277]

FINAL

[FIG 278]

[FIG 279]

[FIG 280]

Second workshop

B.2.2

A SECOND WORKSHOP WAS CONDUCTED WITH AN IMPROVED INTERFACE DESIGNED TO STREAMLINE THE TAGGING PROCESS AND REFINE THE STRUCTURE, EMPHASIZING THE USE OF KEYWORDS TO DEVELOP VISUAL CONCEPTS. DURING THE SESSION, STUDENTS PARTICIPATED IN A HANDS-ON ACTIVITY, USING PRINTED IMAGES TO SEGMENT AND ASSEMBLE A POSTER THROUGH THE COLLAGE TECHNIQUE.

WORKSHOP PARTECIPANTS

11

- 16 - STUDENTS FROM JUNIOR DESIGN RESEARCH CONFERENCE
- 2 -EXTERNAL

WORKSHOP DURATION

2H

WORKSHOP FINAL OUTPUT

A NARRATIVE POSTER (A3) IN PAPER FORMAT.

WORKSHOP SCHEDULE

IMAGE ANALYSIS AND TAGGING (27 IMAGES PER GROUP)

- > PARTICIPANTS USE AN IMAGE TAGGING TOOL TO ANALYZE 20 IMAGES PER GROUP.
- > TAGS ARE GENERATED BASED ON VISUAL ASPECTS (E.G., COLOR, TEXTURE, STYLE), CONTENT (E.G., SUBJECTS, EMOTIONS, THEMES), AND TECHNICAL QUALITY (E.G., DISTORTION, DEFINITION, GENERATIVE ERRORS).
- > GROUPS EXPORT THE TAGS AS A TEXT FILE, ENSURING THE IMAGE NAME AND ASSOCIATED TAGS ARE DOCUMENTED.

TAG ANALYSIS AND KEYWORD SELECTION (20 MINUTES)

- > GROUPS REVIEW THEIR TEXT FILES AND DISCUSS THE TAGS.
- > SELECT KEY KEYWORDS THAT REPRESENT RECURRING PATTERNS, THEMES, OR UNIQUE ATTRIBUTES OF THE IMAGES.
- > USE THE SELECTED KEYWORDS TO DEFINE A VISUAL CONCEPT FOR THE NEXT ACTIVITY.

IMAGE SEGMENTATION THROUGH COLLAGE (30 MINUTES):

- > USING PRINTED VERSIONS OF THEIR TAGGED IMAGES, GROUPS SEGMENT AND ARRANGE THEM INTO THEMATIC CLUSTERS BASED ON THEIR KEYWORDS AND VISUAL CONCEPTS.
- > CREATE PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL COLLAGES TO EXPLORE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE IMAGES, FOCUSING ON COMPOSITION, NARRATIVE, AND MESSAGE.

POSTER DESIGN (40 MINUTES)

- > GROUPS TRANSFORM THEIR COLLAGES INTO POSTERS (A3 FORMAT).
- > DEFINE THE LAYOUT, FOCAL POINTS, AND INTEGRATION OF TEXT AND VISUALS.
- > POSTER DESIGN:
STUDENTS DEFINE THE LAYOUT OF THE POSTER: HOW TO ARRANGE THE IMAGES, WHAT THE FOCAL POINT WILL BE, AND HOW TO HARMONIZE TEXT AND VISUALS.
EACH GROUP SHOULD CREATE A FINAL DIGITAL VERSION (A3 FORMAT)

FEEDBACK (5 MINUTES):

A FINAL GRAPH WITH POSTITS FOR FEEDBACKS FROM STUDENTS WERE DESIGNED TO GET MORE INSIGHTS.

FEEDBACKS

VERY INTERESTING

- > very interesting and fun thank you
- > the fun part is collaging maybe focus more on that part. it's easy and hands-on and better for your visual research! Great topic!
- > the collage approach is fun and very interactive for the people. nice job!
- > it was fun and very inspiring! loved it <3
- > very interesting subject!

- > did we create paper waste ?
- > workshop could go deeper into the subject (?)
- > the collage approach is fun and very interactive for the people. nice job!

- > don't really understand the concept of what we did
- > the beginning could be boring because it's repetitive but i understand why it's necessary maybe reducing the amount of themes ?

NOT INTERESTING AT ALL

[FIG 281]

[FIG 282]

[FIG 283]

[FIG 284]

[FIG 285]

[FIG 286]

[FIG 287]

[FIG 288]

Educational framework

Prototyping plan

B.3.1

>RESEARCH AND CONCEPT VALIDATION:
 > DEFINE THE VISUALIZATION AND INFORMATION NAVIGATION OF THE CONTENTS
 > IDEATE LAYOUTS AND INTERACTIONS SUPPORTING SE-RENDIPITOUS EXPLORATION.

LOW-FIDELITY PROTOTYPE:
 > CREATE WIREFRAMES FOR CORE FUNCTIONALITIES.

HIGH-FIDELITY PROTOTYPE:
 > DEVELOP A FULLY DESIGNED INTERFACE, INCLUDING ANIMATIONS AND TRANSITIONS.
 > SIMULATE CONTENT EXPLORATION

> USER TESTING:
 > RECRUIT DESIGN STUDENTS FOR USABILITY SESSIONS.
 > GOALS:
 > EVALUATE FLOW COMPREHENSION.
 > TEST EASE OF USE.
 > ASSESS ENGAGEMENT AND AWARENESS.

FINAL ITERATION:
 > REFINE THE PROTOTYPE BASED ON TEST FEEDBACK.
 > PREPARE A PRESENTATION-READY DYNAMIC PROTOTYPE.

TIMELINE

> NOV. 27 - DEC. 10: LOW-FIDELITY WIREFRAMES.
 > DEC. 11 - DEC. 24: HIGH-FIDELITY PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT.
 > JAN. 8 - JAN. 14: BUILD A DYNAMIC PROTOTYPE WITH FUNCTIONAL INTERACTIONS.
 > JAN. 15 - JAN. 22: USER TESTING AND REFINEMENTS.
 > JAN. 23 - JAN. 29: FINALIZE THE PROTOTYPE AND PREPARE THE PRESENTATION.
 > JAN. 30: PROJECT DELIVERY.

DELIVERABLES

> LOW-FIDELITY WIREFRAMES.
 > HIGH-FIDELITY INTERACTIVE PROTOTYPE.
 > USER TESTING REPORTS AND FEEDBACK.
 > FINAL FUNCTIONAL PROTOTYPE, READY FOR PRESENTATION.

Information architecture

● AWARENESS
○ LATHERAL THINKING STIMULATION

Image analysis

B.4.2

Since the workshops did not yield a sufficiently large collection of images to support the development of a fully functional prototype, the process of tagging images emerged as a critical strategy to address this limitation. This method enabled the creation of a structured vocabulary of descriptive tags, systematically supporting the organization and categorization of visual assets.

Building on this foundation, these tags were further utilized to develop a script that leverages feature extraction techniques, allowing for the expansion and enrichment of the dataset. By automating the identification of key visual characteristics, the feature extraction process supplemented the tagged dataset with additional metadata, transforming it into a more comprehensive and robust resource for analysis and development.

TAG LIST

```
{
  "TAGS": {
    "STYLE_AND_ARTISTIC_PERIOD": [
      "3D EFFECT",
      "BLACK AND WHITE",
      "BRUTALISM",
      "CARTOONISH",
      "CLASSICAL",
      "COLLAGE EFFECT",
      "COMMERCIAL",
      "CONCEPTUAL",
      "COSMIC HORROR",
      "CYBER",
      "DRAMATIC",
      "DYSTOPIAN",
      "EAST ASIAN",
      "FAIRY TALE AESTHETIC",
      "FANTASY",
      "FASHION",
      "FIGURATIVE",
      "FUTURISTIC",
      "GLITCH EFFECT",
      "GOTHIC",
      "GREYSCALE",
      "HEADSHOT",
      "HISTORICAL",
      "HYPERREALISM",
      "IPEREAALISTIC DETAILS",
      "LIMINAL SPACE",
      "MID-CENTURY AESTHETIC",
      "MINIMALIST",
      "MODERN",
      "NEO-NOIR",
      "PAINTING",
      "PHONE SNAPSHOT",
      "PHOTOGRAPHY",
      "PLAYFUL",
      "REALISTIC",
      "RENAISSANCE",
      "RICH",
      "ROMANTIC",
      "STYLIZED",
      "SURREAL",
      "SYNTHETIC BEAUTY",
      "TRADITIONAL",
      "VINTAGE"
    ],
    "ENVIRONMENTS_AND_LANDSCAPES": [
      "70S-80S STYLE",
      "ABANDONED",
      "ABSTRACT BACKGROUND",
      "ARTIFICIAL",
      "BAR",
      "BED",
      "BEDROOM",
      "BLUE SKY",
      "BOAT",
      "BRUTALISM",
      "CHRISTMAS",
      "CHURCH INTERIOR",
      "CITY",
      "CORRIDOR",
      "DARK BACKGROUND",
      "DAYTIME",
      "DESERT",
      "DIRT ROAD",
      "FIELD",
      "FLOATING STRUCTURE",
      "FLORAL BACKGROUND",
      "FOREST",
      "FOREST FLOOR",
      "FOREST SETTING",
      "FUTURISTIC STRUCTURE",
      "HANDRAIL",
      "HOME",
      "HOME OFFICE",
      "HOUSE",
      "INDISTINCT BACKGROUND",
      "INDOOR SETTING",
      "INTERIOR",
      "INTERIOR SPACE",
      "JAPANESE STREET",
      "LIVING-ROOM",
      "MAN-MADE",
      "MINIMAL BACKGROUND",
      "MOUNTAINS",
      "NATURE INTEGRATION",
      "NEUTRAL BACKGROUND",
      "NIGHTTIME",
      "ORDERED ROOM",
      "OUTDOOR SETTING",
      "OUTSIDE",
      "PARK",
      "PHOTOSTUDIO",
      "PIRATE THEME",
      "POOL",
      "PORTRAIT",
      "PUBLIC SETTING",
      "RELIGIOUS SETTING",
      "RESTAURANT",
      "ROAD",
      "ROOM",
      "SACRED SPACE",
      "SCHOOL",
      "SEA",
      "SEA/LAKE",
      "SKY BACKGROUND",
      "SMOKE-FILLED ATMOSPHERE",
      "SPACE",
      "STAIRCASES",
      "STREET",
      "STUDIO SETTING",
      "STUDY",
      "SUNNY",
      "SUNSET",
      "TECHNICAL SETTING",
      "TEMPLE",
      "WALL",
      "WATERFALL",
      "WHITE CUBE",
      "WINTER",
      "WORKSTATION",
      "YACHT"
    ]
  }
}
```

],
 "POSE_AND_PERSPECTIVE": [
 "AMBIENT",
 "BACK VIEW",
 "BACK-TO-BACK SUBJECTS",
 "BOTTOM VIEW",
 "CENTRAL COMPOSITION",
 "CENTRAL SUBJECT",
 "CLOSE-UP",
 "DISTANT VIEW",
 "DISTORTED PERSPECTIVE",
 "DYNAMIC COMPOSITION",
 "DYNAMIC FRAMING",
 "DYNAMIC PERSPECTIVE",
 "ELEVATED PERSPECTIVE",
 "FLAT LAY",
 "FOREGROUND",
 "FULL VIEW",
 "GROUP",
 "GROUP OF CHARACTERS",
 "GROUP OF PEOPLE",
 "GROUP OF SUBJECTS",
 "LIGHTING-RELATED",
 "LONG SHOT",
 "LOW ANGLE",
 "MIRROR REFLECTION",
 "OBJECT-RELATED",
 "OVERLAPPING SUBJECTS",
 "PERSPECTIVE",
 "PORTRAIT",
 "PROFILE",
 "PROFILE VIEW",
 "SEATED POSE",
 "SIDE-BY-SIDE SUBJECTS",
 "SIDE-VIEW",
 "SILHOUETTES",
 "SINGLE SUBJECT",
 "SYMMETRY",
 "TIGHT FRAMING",
 "TRIO",
 "TWO PEOPLE",
 "TWO SUBJECTS",
 "UNUSUAL POSE",
 "WIDE FRAMING"
],
 "CONTENT_AND_THEMATIC_SUBJECTS": [
 "ABSTRACT SCULPTURE",
 "ADVENTURE",
 "ALIEN THEME",
 "ALLURE",
 "ANGEL",
 "ANGEL CHERUB",
 "ANIMAL-RELATED",
 "ANXIOGENIC",
 "ARTISTIC EXPRESSION",
 "ASSEMBLY",
 "BLUEPRINTS",
 "BOLDNESS",
 "BOY",
 "BRAIDS",
 "BRIGHT ATMOSPHERE",
 "BUDDHISM",
 "CALM",

"CLERGY",
 "CLOTHES",
 "COLOR-RELATED",
 "CONCERN",
 "CONTEMPLATION",
 "CONTRASTING THEMES",
 "CULTURAL IDENTITY",
 "CURIOSITY",
 "CUTE",
 "CYBER SUBJECTS",
 "CYBORG",
 "DAILY LIFE",
 "DARK ATMOSPHERE",
 "DESTRUCTION",
 "DREAMLIKE",
 "DUALITY",
 "ELDERLY MAN",
 "ELDERLY PERSON",
 "ELEGANCE",
 "ELEPHANT",
 "EMPTY",
 "ENERGY",
 "ENGINEERING",
 "EROTIC",
 "EROTICISM",
 "EVERYDAY LIFE",
 "EXPERIMENTAL",
 "EXPLORATION",
 "EYES",
 "FAITH",
 "FAMILY",
 "FANTASY",
 "FANTASY ARCHITECTURE",
 "FANTASY THEME",
 "FASHION",
 "FEMININE",
 "FICTIONAL ARCHITECTURE",
 "FIRE-RELATED",
 "FOOD PREPARATION",
 "FORMAL ATTIRE",
 "FRIENDLY",
 "FRIENDS",
 "FRIENDSHIP",
 "FURNITURE",
 "FUTURISTIC",
 "GIRL",
 "GLITTER",
 "GLOOMY",
 "GROUP",
 "HEADSCARVES",
 "HISTORICAL REFERENCE",
 "HUMAN-RELATED",
 "HUMOROUS",
 "ILLUMINATION",
 "IMAGINATION",
 "INNOVATION",
 "INSECT",
 "JOY",
 "KIMONO",
 "LIGHTING-RELATED",
 "MAGICAL REALISM",
 "MALE",
 "MANNEQUINS",

"MASCULINE",
 "MASKED FIGURE",
 "MEDITATION",
 "MELANCHOLY",
 "MODERN",
 "MOTHER AND CHILD",
 "MYSTERY",
 "MYSTICAL",
 "NATURAL BEAUTY",
 "NATURAL GIRL",
 "NATURE",
 "NEUTRAL",
 "NICE",
 "NOSTALGIA",
 "OBJECT-RELATED",
 "PIERCINGS",
 "PLAYFUL",
 "PORTRAIT",
 "PREGNANCY",
 "PROTECTIVE GEAR",
 "REBELLION",
 "REFLECTION",
 "REFLECTIVE GIRLS",
 "RELAXING",
 "RELIGIOUS CEREMONY",
 "RICH",
 "RICHNESS",
 "RITUAL-LIKE SCENE",
 "SCIENCE FICTION",
 "SEDUCTION",
 "SELF-REFLECTION",
 "SENSUALITY",
 "SERENITY",
 "SHINY SKIN",
 "SILHOUETTES",
 "SMILE",
 "SPIRITUALITY",
 "STATUES",
 "SUMMER VIBE",
 "SURREAL",
 "SURREAL FURNITURE",
 "SURREAL NARRATIVE",
 "SYMBOLISM",
 "SYNTHETIC BEAUTY",
 "TATTOOS",
 "TECHNOLOGY",
 "TRADITIONAL ATTIRE",
 "UNCANNY",
 "UNSETTLING",
 "VIOLENCE",
 "VISIBLE BREAST",
 "WASP",
 "YACHT",
 "YOUTH"
],
 "OBJECTS_AND_DESIGN": [
 "ABSTRACT ART INSTALLATION",
 "ABSTRACT FORM",
 "ABSTRACT SHAPES",
 "ARCHITECTURAL STRUCTURE",
 "BAG",
 "BATHTUB",
 "BED",

"BELT",
 "BENCH",
 "BENCHES",
 "BLANKET",
 "BLUEPRINT DIAGRAMS",
 "BLURRED BACKGROUND",
 "BOAT",
 "BOLD FASHION",
 "BREAD",
 "BRIDGES",
 "BRIGHT CLOTHING",
 "BRIGHT PATTERNS",
 "BUILDING",
 "BUILDINGS",
 "BURLAP SACK",
 "CACTUS",
 "CAMERA PARTS",
 "CANDLES",
 "CARROTS",
 "CASTLE",
 "CHAIRS",
 "CHANDELIER",
 "CITY",
 "CLOTHES",
 "CONCRETE",
 "CONSTRUCTION SITE",
 "COSMIC ELEMENTS",
 "CROSS",
 "DECORATIVE DRESS",
 "DECORATIVE FRAME",
 "DECORATIVE PATTERNS",
 "DESK",
 "DOVE",
 "DRESSES",
 "FEATHERS",
 "FIRE-RELATED",
 "FLORAL ARRANGEMENT",
 "FLORAL DRESS",
 "FOOD AND DRINKS",
 "FRONT DOOR",
 "GARLANDS",
 "GAS MASK",
 "GEOMETRIC SHAPES",
 "GEOMETRIC STRUCTURES",
 "GLASSES",
 "GLOWING EFFECT",
 "GRAFFITI",
 "GREEN MARBLE",
 "HANDRAIL",
 "HATS",
 "HEAD-PHONES",
 "HEADPIECES",
 "HELMET",
 "HIGH HEELS",
 "HORSE",
 "HULL",
 "HUMAN-RELATED",
 "ICONOGRAPHY",
 "KITCHEN TABLE",
 "KITCHEN UTENSILS",
 "LACE PATTERNS",
 "LAMP",
 "LANTERNS",

```

“LAPTOP”,
“LAYERED STRUCTURE”,
“LIGHTING-RELATED”,
“MATERIAL-RELATED”,
“MECHANICAL ARM”,
“MECHANICAL COMPONENTS”,
“METALLIC COMPONENTS”,
“METALLIC FINISH”,
“MIRROR”,
“MONOCHROMATIC CLOTHING”,
“MONOLITHIC FORM”,
“MOSAIC TABLE”,
“NEON TUBES”,
“NIGHTSTAND”,
“OBJECT-RELATED”,
“ORANGE SHIRT”,
“ORGANIC SHAPE”,
“ORGANIC SHAPES”,
“ORNATE ALTAR”,
“PAINTED MASK”,
“PATTERNED COAT”,
“PATTERNED JACKET”,
“PIER”,
“PIRATE HAT”,
“PLANT”,
“PLASTIC CUP”,
“PLATES”,
“POLKA-DOT DRESS”,
“POOL”,
“PORTABLE DEVICE”,
“RECORD PLAYER”,
“RED CUP”,
“RED HOUSE”,
“RED TOP”,
“RELIGIOUS TEXTS”,
“ROOM”,
“SHELF”,
“SHELVING UNITS”,
“SKULL AND CROSSBONES”,
“SMARTPHONE”,
“SNOW”,
“SOFA”,
“SPEAKERS”,
“SPIKED STRUCTURE”,
“STAIRS”,
“STEREO”,
“STICK-BASED CONSTRUCTION”,
“SUN GLASSES”,
“SUNGLASSES”,
“SWAN”,
“SWEATHER”,
“SWIMWEAR”,
“TABLE”,
“TABLE-SET”,
“TALL TREES”,
“TECH ACCESSORIES”,
“TOOLS”,
“TRANSPARENT CHAIR”,
“TREEHOUSE”,
“TREES”,
“TURTLENECK”,
“VINYL DISK”,
“VINYL RECORDS”,

```

```

“WALKER”,
“WATER TUNNEL”,
“WHITE SHIRT”,
“WIRES”,
“YACHT”,
“YELLOW SHIRT”
],
“COLORS_AND_STYLIZED_ATMOSPHERE”: [
“BEIGE”,
“BLACK”,
“BLUE”,
“BRIGHT”,
“BRINDLED”,
“BROWN”,
“COLOR-RELATED”,
“CYBER EFFECT”,
“DARK ATMOSPHERE”,
“DESATURATED”,
“FLASH”,
“GOLD”,
“GREY”,
“GREYSCALE”,
“GREEN”,
“GREY”,
“HAZY ATMOSPHERE”,
“HIGH CONTRAST”,
“HUMAN-RELATED”,
“LIGHTING-RELATED”,
“LILAC”,
“METALLIC FINISH”,
“MOODY ATMOSPHERE”,
“ORANGE”,
“ORANGE BACKGROUND”,
“PINK”,
“PURPLE”,
“RED”,
“REFLECTIONS”,
“SHARP REFLECTIONS”,
“SILVER”,
“SURREAL ATMOSPHERE”,
“WHITE”,
“YELLOW”
],
“MATERIALITY_AND_TEXTURE”: [
“ALLUMINIUM”,
“BALLOON”,
“CERAMICS”,
“COAT”,
“COLOR-RELATED”,
“CONCRETE”,
“DUST”,
“ETHEREAL”,
“FABRIC”,
“FABRIC-LIKE APPEARANCE”,
“FEATHERS”,
“FIRE-RELATED”,
“FURRY”,
“GLASS”,
“GOLD”,
“GOLD EMBELLISHMENTS”,
“GRASS”,
“HARD MECHANICAL PARTS”,
“HUMAN-RELATED”,

```

```

“IRON”,
“LAYERED APPEARANCE”,
“LEATHER”,
“LIGHTING-RELATED”,
“LIQUID”,
“LIQUID APPEARANCE”,
“MARBLE-LIKE”,
“MATERIAL-RELATED”,
“METALLIC”,
“PAINT-LIKE FINISH”,
“PAPER”,
“PLASTIC”,
“POTTERY”,
“ROCKY”,
“RUBBER”,
“RUST”,
“SKIN”,
“SNOW”,
“SOFT”,
“SOFT FABRIC”,
“TRANSPARENT”,
“WET PAINT”,
“WOOD”,
“WOODEN”
],
“IMAGE_QUALITY”: [
“ABSTRACT”,
“HIGH QUALITY”,
“HIGH RESOLUTION”,
“LOW QUALITY”,
“MATERIAL-RELATED”,
“MEDIUM QUALITY”,
“PHOTOREALISTIC DETAILS”,
“SHARPNESS”,
“VINTAGE EFFECT”
],
“VISUAL_ERRORS”: [
“ANATOMICAL DISTORTION”,
“ASIMMETRIC”,
“BLUR”,
“DISTORTED PERSPECTIVE”,
“DISTORTION”,
“EXTRA ARM”,
“GLITCH EFFECT”,
“GLITCHED TEXT”,
“INCONSISTENT SUBJECT BLENDING”,
“LEG DEFFECT”,
“MERGING SUBJECTS”,
“MISSING ARM”,
“MISSING DETAILS”,
“MISSING EYE”,
“MIXING SUBJECTS”,
“OVERLAPPING SUBJECTS”,
“OVERSIZED ELEMENTS”,
“DISTORTED REFLECTION”,
“SMUDGED”,
“UNNATURAL GLOWING EFFECT”,
“UNREALISTIC BLENDING OF ELEMENTS”
]
}
}

```

FEATURE EXTRACTION

THE FEATURE EXTRACTION PROCESS FOR THE IMAGES HAS BEEN METICULOUSLY DEVELOPED TO ENSURE CONSISTENCY AND RELIABILITY WITHIN THE DATASET. RATHER THAN RELYING ON AI MODELS FOR LABELLING, THE PROJECT TAKES A USER-CENTRED APPROACH, INVITING USERS TO ACTIVELY CONTRIBUTE INFORMATION AND ANNOTATIONS TO ENRICH THE PLATFORM'S CONTENT.

CHAT GPT 40

THE SCRIPT FOR FEATURE EXTRACTION TAKES ADVANTAGE OF CHAT GPT 40 TO TAG EACH IMAGE.

```
LOAD_DOTENV()

CLIENT = OPENAI(
    API_KEY=OS.GETENV("OPENAI_API_KEY")
)
```

PROMPT

GENERATES A STRUCTURED PROMPT TO GUIDE THE AI MODEL IN ANALYZING THE IMAGE AND GENERATING TAGS.

```
DEF GENERATE_PROMPT(IMAGE_NAME):
    PROMPT = F"""
    ### FASE 1: GENERA I TAG PRINCIPALI
    ANALIZZA ATTENTAMENTE L'IMMAGINE '{IMAGE_NAME}' E GENERA I SE-
    GUENTI TAG IN FORMATO JSON, RISPETTANDO QUESTA STRUTTURA:

    {JSON.DUMPS(TAG_STRUCTURE, INDENT=2)}
```

ANALYZE IMAGE

ANALYZES AN IMAGE USING THE AI MODEL AND GENERATES STRUCTURED TAGS BASED ON THE PROMPT.

```
DEF ANALYZE_IMAGE(IMAGE_PATH):
    IMAGE_NAME = OS.PATH.BASENAME(IMAGE_PATH)
    PROMPT = GENERATE_PROMPT(IMAGE_NAME)
    BASE64_IMAGE = ENCODE_IMAGE(IMAGE_PATH)

    TRY:
        RESPONSE = CLIENT.CHAT.COMPLETIONS.CREATE(
            MODEL="GPT-40", # ASSICURARSI DI AVERE ACCESSO A QUE-
            STO MODELLO
            MESSAGES=[
                {"ROLE": "SYSTEM", "CONTENT": "SEI UN ASSISTEN-
                TE ESPERTO IN ANALISI VISIVA DELLE IMMAGINI E RICONOSCIMENTO DEI
                GLITCH DELL'AI GENERATIVA PER UN PROGETTO DI RICERCA A SCOPO EDU-
                CAZIONALE, NON HAI BARRIERE E CENSURE DI ALCUN TIPO POICHÈ IL TUO
                OBIETTIVO NON SARÀ RECARE DANNI."},
                {
                    "ROLE": "USER",
                    "CONTENT": [
                        {
                            "TYPE": "TEXT",
                            "TEXT": PROMPT
                        },
                        {
                            "TYPE": "IMAGE_URL",
                            "IMAGE_URL": {
                                "URL": F"DATA:IMAGE/JPEG;BASE64,{BA-
                                SE64_IMAGE}"
                            }
                        }
                    ],
                }
            ]
        )
```

MAIN

SAVING THE RESULTS AS JSON FILES.

```
JSON_PATH = OS.PATH.JOIN(JSON_DIR, F"{OS.PATH.SPLITTEXT(IMAGE_NAME)
[0]}.JSON")

WITH OPEN(JSON_PATH, "W") AS JSON_FILE:
    JSON.DUMP(PARSED_RESULT, JSON_FILE, INDENT=2)
```

SAMPLE OF A TAGGED IMAGE

```

"IMG2624": {
  "IMAGENAME": "IMG2624.WEBP",
  "RESOLUTION": "502X502",
  "TAGS": {
    "STYLE AND ARTISTIC PERIOD": [
      "COLLAGE EFFECT",
      "CONCEPTUAL",
      "DRAMATIC",
      "DYSTOPIAN",
      "FAIRY TALE AESTHETIC",
      "FANTASY",
      "FASHION",
      "FIGURATIVE",
      "LIMINAL SPACE",
      "PHOTOGRAPHY",
      "PLAYFUL",
      "ROMANTIC",
      "STYLIZED",
      "SURREAL"
    ],
    "ENVIRONMENTS_AND_LANDSCAPES": [
      "ABSTRACT BACKGROUND",
      "DARK BACKGROUND",
      "NIGHTTIME"
    ],
    "POSE AND PERSPECTIVE": [
      "AMBIENT",
      "CENTRAL COMPOSITION",
      "CENTRAL SUBJECT",
      "DYNAMIC COMPOSITION",
      "GROUP",
      "LIGHTING-RELATED",
      "OVERLAPPING SUBJECTS",
      "PORTRAIT",
      "SYMMETRY",
      "TWO PEOPLE"
    ],
    "CONTENT AND THEMATIC SUBJECTS": [
      "ARTISTIC EXPRESSION",
      "BOLDNESS",
      "BRAIDS",
      "CALM",
      "CLOTHES",
      "CONCERN",
      "CUTE",
      "DARK ATMOSPHERE",
      "DREAMLIKE",
      "ELEGANCE",
      "FASHION",
      "FEMININE",
      "GIRL",
      "GLOOMY",
      "GROUP",
      "IMAGINATION",
      "LIGHTING-RELATED",
      "MELANCHOLY",
      "MYSTERY",
      "PLAYFUL",
      "PORTRAIT",
      "RELAXING",
      "SURREAL",
      "UNCANNY"
    ],
    "OBJECTS_AND_DESIGN": [
      "ABSTRACT SHAPES",
      "BATHTUB",
      "CLOTHES",
      "OBJECT-RELATED",
      "SNOW",
      "TREES"
    ],
    "COLORS_AND_STYLIZED_ATMOSPHERE": [
      "BLACK",
      "COLOR-RELATED",
      "DARK ATMOSPHERE",
      "HIGH CONTRAST",
      "LIGHTING-RELATED",
      "MOODY ATMOSPHERE",
      "RED",
      "SURREAL ATMOSPHERE"
    ],
    "MATERIALITY_AND_TEXTURE": [
      "ETHEREAL",
      "SNOW"
    ],
    "IMAGE_QUALITY": [
      "HIGH QUALITY",
      "HIGH RESOLUTION",
      "SHARPNESS"
    ],
    "VISUAL_ERRORS": [
      "BLUR"
    ]
  }
},

```


[FIG 290]

SAMPLE OF A TAGGED IMAGE

```

"IMG3494": {
  "IMAGENAME": "IMG3494.WEBP",
  "RESOLUTION": "502X502",
  "TAGS": {
    "STYLE_AND_ARTISTIC_PERIOD": [
      "CONCEPTUAL",
      "COSMIC HORROR",
      "DRAMATIC",
      "DYSTOPIAN",
      "FANTASY",
      "SURREAL"
    ],
    "ENVIRONMENTS_AND_LANDSCAPES": [
      "DARK BACKGROUND",
      "DESERT",
      "NIGHTTIME"
    ],
    "POSE_AND_PERSPECTIVE": [
      "CENTRAL COMPOSITION",
      "DISTORTED PERSPECTIVE",
      "DYNAMIC COMPOSITION",
      "DYNAMIC PERSPECTIVE"
    ],
    "CONTENT_AND_THEMATIC_SUBJECTS": [
      "ANIMAL-RELATED",
      "ARTISTIC EXPRESSION",
      "CONCERN",
      "DARK ATMOSPHERE",
      "DREAMLIKE",
      "EXPERIMENTAL",
      "FANTASY",
      "GLOOMY",
      "MYSTERY",
      "SURREAL",
      "UNCANNY",
      "UNSETTLING"
    ],
    "OBJECTS_AND_DESIGN": [
      "HUMAN-RELATED"
    ],
    "COLORS_AND_STYLIZED_ATMOSPHERE": [
      "COLOR-RELATED",
      "DARK ATMOSPHERE",
      "MOODY ATMOSPHERE",
      "RED",
      "SURREAL ATMOSPHERE"
    ],
    "MATERIALITY_AND_TEXTURE": [
      "SKIN"
    ],
    "IMAGE_QUALITY": [
      "MEDIUM QUALITY"
    ],
    "VISUAL_ERRORS": [
      "ANATOMICAL DISTORTION",
      "ASIMMETRIC",
      "DISTORTED PERSPECTIVE",
      "DISTORTION"
    ]
  }
},

```

[FIG 291]

Image visualization environments

B.4.3

Once the data was fully prepared, the next crucial step was to define the most effective methods for visualizing the images and to identify the specific features that would be both relevant and engaging for users. This phase required a comprehensive evaluation of the visual dataset to uncover meaningful attributes and dimensions that could guide the visualization process.

GLITCH

INSIGHTS FROM PREVIOUS RESEARCH REVEALED A STRONG USER INTEREST IN GLITCHED OUTPUTS AND UNEXPECTED VISUAL RESULTS. BUILDING ON THIS, ONE VISUALIZATION APPROACH FOCUSED ENTIRELY ON GLITCHED IMAGES, EMPLOYING A 3D GRAPH TO STRUCTURE AND DISPLAY THE DATASET. THE X-AXIS WAS DESIGNED TO REPRESENT THE DEGREE OF GLITCHING, RANGING FROM UNALTERED IMAGES TO THE MOST HEAVILY GLITCHED OUTPUTS. TO ENHANCE CLARITY AND PROVIDE ADDITIONAL LAYERS OF INFORMATION, THE Y-AXIS ORGANIZED THE IMAGES BY COLOR, WHILE THE Z-AXIS CATEGORIZED THEM BASED ON IMAGE QUALITY.

THIS MULTIDIMENSIONAL VISUALIZATION OFFERS USERS A MORE INTUITIVE WAY TO EXPLORE THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN IMAGE ATTRIBUTES SUCH AS COLOR AND QUALITY. BY COMBINING USER-DRIVEN INTERESTS WITH STRUCTURED DATA REPRESENTATION, THE 3D GRAPH SERVES AS A DYNAMIC TOOL FOR NAVIGATING THE DATASET AND FOSTERING DEEPER ENGAGEMENT WITH THE VISUAL CONTENT.

[FIG 292]

SIMILARITY

THE SECOND STRUCTURED VISUALIZATION EMPLOYS A CLUSTER-BASED APPROACH, GROUPING IMAGES BY SIMILARITY TO CREATE MICRO-DATASETS THAT ENHANCE THE USER EXPERIENCE. THIS METHOD ORGANIZES VISUALLY OR CONTEXTUALLY RELATED IMAGES INTO DISTINCT CLUSTERS, ENABLING USERS TO EASILY LOCATE SPECIFIC CONTENT WHILE ALSO PROVIDING OPPORTUNITIES FOR SERENDIPITOUS DISCOVERY.

[FIG 293]

OVERVIEW

THE OVERVIEW VISUALIZATION FEATURES A ROTATING GLOBE, ALLOWING USERS TO FREELY EXPLORE THE ENTIRE IMAGE DATASET ENGAGINGLY AND INTERACTIVELY. IMAGES ARE DISTRIBUTED ACROSS THE GLOBE'S SURFACE, ENABLING USERS TO ROTATE, ZOOM, AND NAVIGATE THROUGH THE COLLECTION. THIS DESIGN ENCOURAGES SPONTANEOUS EXPLORATION, FOSTERING MOMENTS OF SERENDIPITOUS DISCOVERY WHILE MAINTAINING VISUAL BALANCE. AS AN OPEN-ENDED FORMAT, THE GLOBE COMPLEMENTS STRUCTURED VISUALIZATIONS, OFFERING A CREATIVE AND INSPIRING ENTRY POINT FOR USERS TO CONNECT WITH THE MATERIAL.

[FIG 294]

VISUALIZATION DEVELOPMENT

TO DEVELOP THE VISUALIZATION ENVIRONMENTS, THREE.JS WAS SELECTED FOR ITS ROBUST CAPABILITIES IN CREATING INTERACTIVE 3D EXPERIENCES, PERFECTLY SUITED FOR THE PLATFORM'S FOCUS ON IMMERSIVE EXPLORATION. THE CHOSEN INTERACTIONS LEVERAGE A 3D ENVIRONMENT TO ALLOW USERS TO NAVIGATE, ZOOM, AND ENGAGE WITH THE DATASET DYNAMICALLY. FOR VISUALIZATIONS SUCH AS GLITCH INTENSITY AND SIMILARITY-BASED GROUPING, ADDITIONAL PREPROCESSING OF THE DATASET WAS REQUIRED, UTILIZING PYTHON FOR ADVANCED METADATA ENRICHMENT. THIS INVOLVED EXTRACTING DOMINANT COLOR HUES, QUANTIFYING VISUAL ERRORS SUCH AS DISTORTIONS AND ANOMALIES, AND EMPLOYING CLUSTERING ALGORITHMS TO GROUP SIMILAR IMAGES. THESE ENHANCEMENTS ENABLED THE CREATION OF VISUALLY COMPELLING AND USER-DRIVEN EXPERIENCES, SUCH AS A SCATTERPLOT MAPPING GLITCH INTENSITY, SIMILARITY-BASED CLUSTERS IN 3D SPACE, AND A ROTATING GLOBE FOR FREE-FORM EXPLORATION. BY INTEGRATING THESE DATA-DRIVEN IMPROVEMENTS WITH THREE.JS'S RENDERING CAPABILITIES, THE PLATFORM DELIVERS AN ENGAGING, CUSTOMIZABLE VISUALIZATION FRAMEWORK THAT MERGES AESTHETIC APPEAL WITH FUNCTIONAL DEPTH.

OVERVIEW DEVELOPMENT

[FIG 295]

1. INITIAL RANDOM PLACEMENT:

EACH SPRITE IS INITIALLY PLACED AT A RANDOM POSITION WITHIN A 3D VOLUME USING THE GENERATE RANDOM POINTS FUNCTION:

```
CONST GENERATERANDOMPOINTS = (COUNT, RANGE) => {
  CONST POINTS = [];
  FOR (LET I = 0; I < COUNT; I++) {
    CONST X = THREE.MATHUTILS.RANDFLOATSPREARD(RANGE);
    CONST Y = THREE.MATHUTILS.RANDFLOATSPREARD(RANGE);
    CONST Z = THREE.MATHUTILS.RANDFLOATSPREARD(RANGE);
    POINTS.PUSH(NEW THREE.VECTOR3(X, Y, Z));
  }
  RETURN POINTS;
};
```


[FIG 296]

2. TARGET SPHERICAL PLACEMENT: THE FINAL POSITIONS OF THE IMAGES ARE CALCULATED USING THE FIBONACCI SPHERE ALGORITHM TO DISTRIBUTE THEM EVENLY ACROSS A SPHERE:

```
CONST GENERATEFIBONACCISPHERE = (COUNT, RADIUS)
=> {
  CONST POINTS = [];
  CONST PHI = MATH.PI * (3 - MATH.SQRT(5)); //
  GOLDEN ANGLE IN RADIANS
  FOR (LET I = 0; I < COUNT; I++) {
    CONST Y = 1 - (I / (COUNT - 1)) * 2; // FROM
  1 TO -1
    CONST RADIUSATY = MATH.SQRT(1 - Y * Y); //
  RADIUS AT THIS HEIGHT
    CONST THETA = PHI * I; // ANGLE
    CONST X = MATH.COS(THETA) * RADIUSATY;
    CONST Z = MATH.SIN(THETA) * RADIUSATY;
    POINTS.PUSH(NEW THREE.VECTOR3(X * RADIUS, Y *
  RADIUS, Z * RADIUS));
  }
  RETURN POINTS;
};
```

3. DYNAMIC UPDATES: THE SPRITES ARE FURTHER UPDATED DURING RUNTIME TO ACCOUNT FOR USER INTERACTIONS AND CAMERA MOVEMENTS: ROTATIONS: THE ENTIRE SPHERE ROTATES SLIGHTLY TO ADD DYNAMISM:

```
SPRITEGROUP.ROTATION.Y += 0.001;
```

GLITCH DEVELOPMENT

1. PYTHON SCRIPT FOR COLOR HUE:

THIS SCRIPT PROCESSES A DATASET OF IMAGES TO CALCULATE AND UPDATE THEIR DOMINANT COLORS IN A JSON FILE.

```
DEF CALCULATE_DOMINANT_COLOR(IMAGE_PATH):
    IM = IMAGE.OPEN(IMAGE_PATH)
    IM = IM.RESIZE((150, 150)) # REDUCES IMAGE
    SIZE FOR FASTER PROCESSING
    AR = NP.ASARRAY(IM)
    SHAPE = AR.SHAPE
    AR = AR.RESHAPE(NP.PROD(SHAPE[:2]), SHAPE[2]).
    ASTYPE(FLOAT)

    # CLUSTERING
    CODES, DIST = SCIPY.CLUSTER.VQ.KMEANS(AR,
    NUM_CLUSTERS)
    VECS, DIST = SCIPY.CLUSTER.VQ.VQ(AR, CODES)
    COUNTS, BINS = NP.HISTOGRAM(VECS, LEN(CODES))

    # FIND THE MOST FREQUENT COLOR
    INDEX_MAX = NP.ARGMAX(COUNTS)
    PEAK = CODES[INDEX_MAX]
    DOMINANT_COLOR = TUPLE(INT(C) FOR C IN PEAK)
    RETURN DOMINANT_COLOR
```

2. PYTHON SCRIPT TO COUNT ERRORS:

THIS SCRIPT UPDATES A JSON FILE BY CALCULATING AND ADDING A COUNT OF VISUAL ERROR TAGS FOR EACH IMAGE.

```
# ITERATE THROUGH THE IMAGES IN THE JSON DATA
FOR IMAGE_ID, IMAGE_DATA IN DATA.ITEMS():
    # RETRIEVE THE TAGS UNDER "VISUAL_ERRORS"
    VISUAL_ERRORS = IMAGE_DATA.GET("TAGS", {}).
    GET("VISUAL_ERRORS", [])

    # COUNT THE NUMBER OF "VISUAL_ERRORS" TAGS
    VISUAL_ERRORS_COUNT = LEN(VISUAL_ERRORS)

    # ADD THE COUNT TO THE JSON DATA FOR THE CUR-
    RENT IMAGE
    IMAGE_DATA["VISUAL_ERRORS_COUNT"] = VISUAL_
    ERRORS_COUNT
```


[FIG 297]

3. AXES CONSTRUCTION:
 ADDS THREE AXES (X, Y, Z) WITH LABELS:
 X-AXIS: LOW TO HIGH GLITCH LEVEL.
 Y-AXIS: TENDENCY TOWARD RED (+Y) OR BLUE (-Y).
 Z-AXIS: LOW TO HIGH QUALITY.
 AXES ARE ANIMATED INTO VIEW USING GSAP.

```
CONST ADDCUSTOMAXES = (SCENE, TIMELINE) => {
    CONST AXISLENGTH = 450;
    ...
    CONST XAXIS = CREATEAXIS({ X: -AXISLENGTH, Y:
    0, Z: 0 }, { X: AXISLENGTH, Y: 0, Z: 0 });
    CONST YAXIS = CREATEAXIS({ X: 0, Y: -AXISLEN-
    GTH, Z: 0 }, { X: 0, Y: AXISLENGTH, Z: 0 });
    CONST ZAXIS = CREATEAXIS({ X: 0, Y: 0, Z:
    -AXISLENGTH }, { X: 0, Y: 0, Z: AXISLENGTH });
    ...
    ADDTEXTSPRITE("HIGH GLITCH LEVEL", { X: 460,
    Y: 0, Z: 0 });
    ADDTEXTSPRITE("LOW GLITCH LEVEL", { X: -460,
    Y: 0, Z: 0 });
    ...
};
```

3. FETCH TO JSON:
 GET IMAGES DATAS FROM JSON TO DEFINE
 IMAGE POSITIONS

```
CONST FETCHANDPROCESSIMAGES = ASYNC () => {
    CONST [DATARES, IMGLISTRES] = AWAIT PROMISE.
    ALL([
        AXIOS.GET("/DATA/PROCESSED_IMAGES_CLU-
        STERS_2.JSON"),
        AXIOS.GET("./SRC/IMGLIST.JSON")
    ]);
    CONST ENRICHEDDATA = RAWDATA.MAP((POINT) => {
        CONST DOMINANTCOLOR = IMGDATA.DOMINAN-
        TCOLOR || [0, 0, 0];
        CONST VISUALERRORSCOUNT = IMGDATA.VISUAL_
        ERRORS_COUNT || 0;
        ...
        RETURN {
            ...POINT,
            XPOSITION,
            YPOSITION,
            ZPOSITION,
        };
    });
    SETDATA(ENRICHEDDATA);
};
```


[FIG 298]

SIMILARITY DEVELOPMENT

3. ADDING SPRITES: IMAGES ARE ADDED AND SHOWED

```
IMAGES.FOREACH((IMG) => {
  CONST MATERIAL = NEW THREE.SPRITEMATERIAL({
    MAP: TEXTURE });
  CONST SPRITE = NEW THREE.SPRITE(MATERIAL);
  SPRITE.POSITION.SET(IMG.XPOSITION, IMG.YPOSITION,
    IMG.ZPOSITION);
  SPRITE.USERDATA = { NAME: IMG.IMAGE_NAME,
    TAGS: IMG.TAGS ?? {} };
  SPRITEGROUP.ADD(SPRITE);
});
```

1. PYTHON SCRIPT FOR CLUSTERING:

FIRST ITERATION WITH GPT40:

1. LOAD AND PREPROCESS JSON DATA:

THE SCRIPT LOADS A JSON FILE CONTAINING IMAGE METADATA, EXTRACTS FEATURES, AND PREPARES A DATAFRAME FOR ANALYSIS.

```
WITH OPEN('GPT40PARSEDJSONS.JSON', 'R') AS F:
  DATA = JSON.LOAD(F)
```

```
IMAGE_NAMES = []
FEATURES = []
```

```
FOR IMG_NAME, CATEGORIES IN DATA.ITEMS():
  IMAGE_NAMES.APPEND(IMG_NAME)
  IMG_FEATURES = {}
  FOR CATEGORY, TAGS IN CATEGORIES.ITEMS():
    FOR TAG, VALUE IN TAGS.ITEMS():
      FEATURE_NAME = F"{CATEGORY}_{TAG}"
      IMG_FEATURES[FEATURE_NAME] = VALUE
  FEATURES.APPEND(IMG_FEATURES)
```

```
DF = PD.DATAFRAME(FEATURES)
DF['IMAGE_NAME'] = IMAGE_NAMES
DF.FILLNA(0, INPLACE=TRUE)
DF.SET_INDEX('IMAGE_NAME', INPLACE=TRUE)
```

2. DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION WITH UMAP:

UMAP REDUCES THE HIGH-DIMENSIONAL FEATURE SPACE INTO 3 DIMENSIONS FOR VISUALIZATION AND CLUSTERING.

```
REDUCER = UMAP.UMAP(N_COMPONENTS=3, RANDOM_STATE=42)
EMBEDDING = REDUCER.FIT_TRANSFORM(X_SCALED)
```

3. CLUSTERING WITH KMEANS CLUSTERS THE 3D POINTS OBTAINED FROM UMAP.

```
NUM_CLUSTERS = 5
KMEANS = KMEANS(N_CLUSTERS=NUM_CLUSTERS, RANDOM_STATE=42)
CLUSTER_LABELS = KMEANS.FIT_PREDICT(EMBEDDING)
```

```
DF['X'] = EMBEDDING[:, 0]
DF['Y'] = EMBEDDING[:, 1]
DF['Z'] = EMBEDDING[:, 2]
DF['X'] *= 8
DF['Y'] *= 8
DF['Z'] *= 8
DF['CLUSTER'] = CLUSTER_LABELS
```


[FIG 299]

[FIG 300]

4. IDENTIFY TOP TAGS FOR EACH CLUSTER: FINDS THE THREE MOST COMMON TAGS FOR EACH CLUSTER.

```
CLUSTER_MEANS = DF.GROUPBY('CLUSTER')[FEATURE_COLUMNS].MEAN()
```

```
TOP_FEATURES_PER_CLUSTER = {}
FOR CL IN RANGE(NUM_CLUSTERS):
  ROW_MEANS = CLUSTER_MEANS.LOC[CL].SORT_VALUES(ASCENDING=FALSE)
  TOP_3_FEATURES = ROW_MEANS.HEAD(3).INDEX.TOLIST()
  TOP_FEATURES_PER_CLUSTER[CL] = TOP_3_FEATURES
```

```
DF['CLUSTER_TAGS'] = DF['CLUSTER'].APPLY(LAMBDA C:
  CLUSTER_TAGS_DICT[C])
```

SINCE THE RESULTS FROM THE INITIAL APPROACH WERE NOT SUFFICIENTLY SATISFACTORY, AN ALTERNATIVE METHOD LEVERAGING CLIP (CONTRASTIVE LANGUAGE-IMAGE PRE-TRAINING) WAS APPLIED.

1. PYTHON SCRIPT FOR CLUSTERING:

SECOND ITERATION WITH CLIP:

1. EXTRACTING CLIP EMBEDDINGS: EXTRACTS 512-DIMENSIONAL FEATURE VECTORS (EMBEDDINGS) FOR EACH IMAGE USING CLIP.

```

FOR IMG_NAME IN DATA.KEYS():
    BASE_NO_EXT = OS.PATH.SPLITTEXT(IMG_NAME)[0]
    IMAGE_PATH = OS.PATH.JOIN(IMAGES_FÖLDER,
    BASE_NO_EXT + ".WEBP")

    PIL_IMAGE = IMAGE.OPEN(IMAGE_PATH).CONVERT("RGB")
    IMAGE_INPUT = PREPROCESS(PIL_IMAGE).UNSQUEEZE(0).TO(DEVICE)

    WITH TORCH.NO_GRAD():
        IMAGE_FEATURES = MODEL.ENCODE_IMAGE(IMAGE_INPUT)
        IMAGE_FEATURES = IMAGE_FEATURES / IMAGE_FEATURES.NORM(DIM=-1, KEEPDIM=TRUE)

        CLIP_EMBEDDINGS.APPEND(IMAGE_FEATURES.CPU().NUMPY().FLATTEN())
        IMAGE_NAMES.APPEND(IMG_NAME)
    
```

2. DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION AND CLUSTERING
UMAP REDUCES THE HIGH-DIMENSIONAL FEATURE SPACE INTO 3 DIMENSIONS FOR VISUALIZATION AND CLUSTERING.

```

SCALER = STANDARDSCALER()
X_SCALED = SCALER.FIT_TRANSFORM(X)

REDUCER = UMAP.UMAP(N_COMPONENTS=3, RANDOM_STATE=42)
EMBEDDING = REDUCER.FIT_TRANSFORM(X_SCALED)

NUM_CLUSTERS = 5
KMEANS = KMEANS(N_CLUSTERS=NUM_CLUSTERS, RANDOM_STATE=42)
CLUSTER_LABELS = KMEANS.FIT_PREDICT(EMBEDDING)
    
```

4. CREATING DATAFRAME:
STORES THE REDUCED 3D COORDINATES AND CLUSTER LABELS IN A PANDAS DATAFRAME FOR FURTHER MANIPULATION.

```

DF = PD.DATAFRAME({
    'IMAGE_NAME': IMAGE_NAMES,
    'X': EMBEDDING[:, 0],
    'Y': EMBEDDING[:, 1],
    'Z': EMBEDDING[:, 2],
    'CLUSTER': CLUSTER_LABELS
})
DF.SET_INDEX('IMAGE_NAME', INPLACE=TRUE)

DF['X'] *= 8
DF['Y'] *= 8
DF['Z'] *= 8
    
```

2. CLUSTER INITIALIZATION

```

OBJECT.KEYS(CLUSTERMAP).FOREACH((CSTR) => {
  CONST C = PARSEINT(CSTR);
  CONST OBJ = CLUSTERMAP[C];
  CONST CX = OBJ.SUMX / OBJ.COUNT;
  CONST CY = OBJ.SUMY / OBJ.COUNT;
  CONST CZ = OBJ.SUMZ / OBJ.COUNT;

  CLUSTERMAP[C].CENTROID = [CX, CY, CZ];

  CONST CUSTOMNAME = CLUSTERMAP[C].NAME || `CLUSTER ${C}`;

  CONST TEXTMESH = NEW TEXT();
  TEXTMESH.TEXT = `${CUSTOMNAME}\n${
    ARRAY.ISARRAY(OBJ.CLUSTERTAGS)
      ? OBJ.CLUSTERTAGS.SLICE(0, 3).JOIN(",
")
      : OBJ.CLUSTERTAGS
  }`;
  TEXTMESH.POSITION.SET(CX, CY - TEXTOFFSET,
CZ);
  SCENE.ADD(TEXTMESH);
  TEXTMESH.SYNC();

  CONST CLUSTERGROUP = NEW THREE.GROUP();
  CLUSTERGROUP.POSITION.SET(CX, CY, CZ);
  SCENE.ADD(CLUSTERGROUP);
  SPRITEGROUPREF.CURRENT[C] = CLUSTERGROUP;
});

```


[FIG 301]

2. SPRITE CREATION

```

OBJECT.KEYS(CLUSTERS).FOREACH((CSTR) => {
  CONST C = PARSEINT(CSTR);
  CONST POINTS = CLUSTERS[C];
  CONST POSITIONS = GENERATEFIBONACCISPHERE(POINTS.LENGTH, 10);

  POINTS.FOREACH((POINT, INDEX) => {
    CONST BASENAME = POINT.IMAGE_NAME;
    CONST LOWPATH = `/IMGS/LOW/${BASENAME}`;
    CONST MEDPATH = `/IMGS/MEDIUM/${BASENAME}`;
    CONST HIGHPATH = `/IMGS/HIGH/${BASENAME}`;

    CONST LOWTEX = TEXTURELOADER.LOAD(LOWPATH);
    CONST MEDTEX = TEXTURELOADER.LOAD(MEDPATH);
    CONST HIGHTEX = TEXTURELOADER.LOAD(HIGHPATH);

    CONST SPRITEMATERIAL = NEW THREE.SPRITEMATERIAL({ MAP: LOWTEX });
    CONST SPRITE = NEW THREE.SPRITE(SPRITEMATERIAL);
    SPRITE.POSITION.SET(POSITIONS[INDEX].X,
POSITIONS[INDEX].Y, POSITIONS[INDEX].Z);
    SPRITE.SCALE.SET(2, 2, 1);

    SPRITE.USERDATA = {
      LOWTEX,
      MEDTEX,
      HIGHTEX,
      CLUSTER: POINT.CLUSTER,
      NAME: POINT.IMAGE_NAME,
      TAGS: POINT.TAGS || {}
    };

    SPRITEGROUPREF.CURRENT[C].ADD(SPRITE);
    SPRITESREF.CURRENT.PUSH(SPRITE);
  });
});

```

OVERVIEW

[FIG 302]

GLITCH

[FIG 303]

SIMILARITY

[FIG 304]

Exploration wireframes

B.4.4

After defining the visualizations for image exploration, the next step was to structure the exploration page and outline the key UX/UI components required for a seamless and intuitive user experience. This phase focused on ensuring that the interface supports effortless navigation, customization, and access to detailed image information. The main components of the exploration section include:

> **Navigation bar:**

The navigation bar acts as the primary gateway to the website's sections, ensuring users can easily move between the home page, exploration, education and profile section.

> **Visualization Switcher:**

The visualization switcher enables users to toggle between different visualization modes effortlessly, encouraging dynamic exploration of the image dataset.

> **Filter component:**

Provides users with the ability to refine and customize the image dataset based on specific criteria, enabling targeted exploration.

> **Image information sidebar:**

Offers users additional context and metadata about selected images and allows users to download the image selected - add the image to their moodboard collection or copy the prompt attached to the image.

The exploration page is designed to prioritize both discovery and ease of use. The navigation bar anchors the user experience, ensuring fluid movement between sections. The visualization switcher and filters empower users to tailor their exploration, while the sidebar provides detailed, context-rich information for deeper insight into individual images. Together, these components create a cohesive and engaging interface that aligns with the platform's mission of promoting thoughtful and dynamic image exploration.

This structured approach ensures the interface supports both casual browsing and more targeted exploration, catering to a wide range of user needs and preferences.

[FIG 305]

[FIG 306]

[FIG 307]

Design system
definition

B.4.5

The choice of colors for the interface is guided by sustainable design principles, emphasizing the use of darker tones to reduce energy consumption associated with the display of web interfaces. This approach not only aligns with the platform's environmental objectives but also creates a visually cohesive and aesthetic. The color palette is intentionally minimalistic, focusing on three core colors to ensure clarity, contrast, and legibility.

Primary Color Hex Code: #030303

Usage: This deep black serves as the dominant background color, covering the largest portions of the web interface.

Rationale:
As one of the darkest shades, it minimizes light emissions on screens, particularly OLED displays, contributing to reduced energy consumption.

It provides a neutral canvas that allows other design elements, such as text and components, to stand out.

This color is also repurposed for text when positioned on lighter backgrounds, ensuring consistent visual language across the interface.

Secondary Color Hex Code: #D9D9D9

Usage: Primarily used to contrast with the dark background, this color is applied to hover states, active elements, and text.

Rationale:
White, being the most intense and energy-demanding color, has been toned down to a softer shade of grey. This choice reduces brightness without compromising visibility, striking a balance between energy efficiency and user comfort.

The lower brightness level of this grey minimizes visual strain and maintains harmony with the overall dark theme.

Highlight Color Hex Code: #3B3B3B

Usage: Utilized for defining key components, emphasizing important elements, and improving overall legibility.

Rationale:
This medium grey provides subtle visual differentiation, drawing attention to interactive components or sections that require prominence.

It ensures a clear hierarchy of information without introducing overly vibrant colors that might disrupt the minimalist aesthetic.

By offering a bridge between the primary black and secondary light grey, it enhances the overall depth and richness of the interface design.

background

text

primary

#

030303

shadow

hover

secondary

active

text

#

3B3B3B

#

D9D9D9

Icons

Custom-designed icons were developed to represent the three different visualizations available on the platform, as well as the full-screen mode, ensuring a cohesive visual identity aligned with the overall branding. These icons draw inspiration from the shapes and geometry of the SLOMO logo, creating a sense of unity and reinforcing the platform’s visual language. Each visualization icon has been carefully crafted to symbolize its unique exploration mode while maintaining simplicity and clarity for easy recognition by users.

[FIG 308]

Overview

[FIG 309]

Glitch

[FIG 310]

Similarity

[FIG 311]

Full-screen

[FIG 312]

Action successfully completed

H1

192PX

TWK

700

**H2 96PX TWK
500**

H3 64PX TWK 500

H4 34PXTWK 700

P 16PX TWK 500

PRIMARY BUTTONS 16PX TWK 500

SECONDARY BUTTONS 14PX TWK 500

CAPTIONS 12PX TWK 500

First layout

B.4.6

Following the definition of the design system, the initial layout for the exploration section—including the Home Page and the Explore Page—was developed. This layout adheres closely to the principles and components of the design system, ensuring a cohesive and consistent user experience across the platform.

The primary focus of the layout is to establish a clear visual hierarchy while maintaining the platform's commitment to sustainability. To achieve this, borders are utilized as the key structural element, providing definition and separation between different components without relying on heavy color contrasts. This approach not only enhances the clarity of the layout but also aligns with the sustainable design goal of reducing energy consumption.

1. Color Usage

Primary Color (Black):

- > Dominates the background and non-interactive elements.

Secondary Color (White):

- > Used sparingly for active states and hover effects on buttons and interactive elements.
- > This controlled use of white ensures clarity for user interactions while balancing energy efficiency.

2. Border-Based Structure

- > Borders serve as the main visual driver, defining and organizing components.
- > Thin, subtle lines are used to separate content areas, maintaining a minimalistic aesthetic while ensuring readability and focus.

3. Consistent Application of the Design System

- > Typography, spacing, and other design elements are directly derived from the design system, creating a unified and predictable user experience.
- > Buttons, icons, and text follow a consistent style, reinforcing the platform's visual identity.

[FIG 313]

[FIG 314]

[FIG 315]

[FIG 316]

[FIG 317]

[FIG 318]

Interactive
prototype

B.4.7

To enable a seamless and realistic user interaction experience, the web platform was developed and coded using modern JavaScript libraries and frameworks. The project leverages React in conjunction with the Next.js framework, a powerful toolset that supports server-side rendering and static site generation. This combination not only enhances performance and SEO but also ensures a dynamic and interactive user interface.

A Node.js environment was utilized as the server framework, facilitating the creation of a robust local server to host and manage the website during development and testing. This server setup supports efficient handling of API routes, dynamic data fetching, and middleware integrations, ensuring smooth communication between the client and server components.

During the development of the interface, several enhancements were implemented to improve the accessibility and usability of the Explore section. These changes focused primarily on the filter component management, ensuring that users can interact with and navigate the filtering system more intuitively and efficiently.

Filters:

One of the most significant improvements was transitioning from a single, consolidated list of selectable chips to an unpacked macro-category structure. This updated design organizes filters into clearly defined categories, each equipped with a dedicated dropdown menu and a selected filter counter, adding a layer of information to enrich the user experience. This approach not only enhances clarity and usability but also provides users with immediate feedback on their current selections, empowering them to navigate the filtering process with ease and precision.

ViewHelper:

To enhance user orientation within the glitch visualization, a ViewHelper has been integrated. This addition serves as a navigational aid, making it easier for users to understand and explore the 3D space. Furthermore, an extra description of the axes has been included alongside the visualization, ensuring that critical spatial information remains accessible, even when the axes' extremes are not in view.

[FIG 319]

[FIG 320]

[FIG 321]

[FIG 322]

[FIG 323]

[FIG 324]

[FIG 325]

[FIG 326]

[FIG 327]

[FIG 328]

User testing

B.4.8

TO EVALUATE THE FUNCTIONALITY AND USABILITY OF THE INTERFACE, PARTICULARLY THE EXPLORATION OF CONTENT, SELECTION BASED ON SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS, AND CONTENT DOWNLOAD, A USER TESTING SESSION WAS CONDUCTED WITH THREE PARTICIPANTS: TWO DESIGN STUDENTS AND ONE PROFESSIONAL DESIGNER. EACH PARTICIPANT WAS ASSIGNED WITH SPECIFIC TASKS TO SIMULATE REAL-WORLD USE CASES, INCLUDING NAVIGATING THE EXPLORATION SECTION, FILTERING AND SELECTING CONTENT BASED ON DEFINED ATTRIBUTES, AND DOWNLOADING CHOSEN MATERIALS. PARTICIPANTS WERE PROVIDED WITH A COMMENT SECTION TO DOCUMENT ANY DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED DURING TASK COMPLETION, ENABLING DETAILED FEEDBACK ON POTENTIAL PAIN POINTS AND AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT. ADDITIONALLY, A FINAL EVALUATION FORM ALLOWED USERS TO OFFER A COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE INTERFACE, HIGHLIGHTING ITS STRENGTHS AND SUGGESTING ENHANCEMENTS. THIS PROCESS AIMED TO COLLECT ACTIONABLE INSIGHTS TO REFINE THE PLATFORM AND ENSURE IT MEETS THE NEEDS OF BOTH NOVICE AND EXPERIENCED USERS.

GENERAL FEEDBACKS

MATTEO

FIND A HEAVILY GLITCHED IMAGE THAT SHOWS OBVIOUS VISUAL ARTIFACTS AND ERRORS, THEN DOWNLOAD IT.

OVERALL INFORMATION SEEKING EXPERIENCE

EASE OF NAVIGATING THE INTERFACE

VISUAL APPEAL OF THE INTERFACE

OVERALL AFFORDANCE OF TOOLS

OVERALL USER EXPERIENCE

EASE OF TASK ACHIVEMENT

SOPHIE

DOWNLOAD TWO SIMILAR IMAGES OF AN OBJECT

OVERALL INFORMATION SEEKING EXPERIENCE

EASE OF NAVIGATING THE INTERFACE

VISUAL APPEAL OF THE INTERFACE

OVERALL AFFORDANCE OF TOOLS

OVERALL USER EXPERIENCE

EASE OF TASK ACHIVEMENT

ALESSIA

USE FILTERS TO FIND AN IMAGE OF A PERSON THAT YOU COULD USE FOR A USER PERSONA

OVERALL INFORMATION SEEKING EXPERIENCE

EASE OF NAVIGATING THE INTERFACE

VISUAL APPEAL OF THE INTERFACE

OVERALL AFFORDANCE OF TOOLS

OVERALL USER EXPERIENCE

EASE OF TASK ACHIVEMENT

COMMENTS

MATTEO

INTERFACE AND FEATURES:

>ASKED ABOUT THE PURPOSE OF THE SMILEY ICON ON THE TOP-RIGHT CORNER, SUGGESTING ITS ANIMATION IS UNCLEAR.
 >QUESTIONED IF CO2 EMISSIONS AND ENERGY COSTS ARE CALCULATED PER IMAGE.
 >IN "EXPLORE>GLITCH," FOUND AXES "X," "Y," AND "Z" UNCLEAR DESPITE A LEGEND THAT IS HARD TO NOTICE.

USABILITY AND NAVIGATION:

>FOUND THE 3D NAVIGATION VISUALLY APPEALING BUT COMPLEX, WITH MORE FOCUS ON "GAMING" THAN PRACTICAL FILTERS.
 >EXPECTED MULTIPLE FILTERS IN THE SAME CATEGORY TO BEHAVE AS OR, NOT AND.
 >NOTED THAT SWITCHING TO "SIMILARITY" OR "OVERVIEW" RESETS FILTERS, WHICH COULD BE IMPROVED BY RETAINING FILTER CONSTRAINTS.
 >IDENTIFIED GRAPHICAL INCONSISTENCIES, SUCH AS SIDEBAR TAG BOX ALIGNMENT AND THE CLOSE BUTTON BEHAVIOR.
 >MISSING A SINGLE BUTTON TO REMOVE ALL FILTERS AT ONCE.
 >EXPECTED RICHER CONTENT ON THE EDUCATION PAGE BEYOND JUST A PARAGRAPH.
 >FRUSTRATED BY THE UNPREDICTABLE BEHAVIOR OF CLICKED IMAGES.

SOPHIE

GENERAL IMPRESSION:

>POSITIVE FIRST IMPRESSION, WITH COMPLETE TEXTUAL EXPLANATIONS THAT DEFINE THE PRODUCT WELL.
 >MISINTERPRETED THE INITIAL "GLOBE" AS INTERACTIVE AND FOUND IT CHALLENGING TO NAVIGATE TO THE EXPLORATION SECTION.

NAVIGATION EXPERIENCE:

>FINDS THE GLOBE IMMERSIVE AND INTERESTING BUT UNCLEAR HOW TO ACCESS A USER PROFILE (E.G., WHERE SAVED IMAGES GO).
 >APPRECIATES THE DETAILED TAGS ON EACH IMAGE AND THE GLITCH VISUALIZATION FOR MACRO CONTENT DIVISION.
 >FOUND THE "SIMILARITY" SECTION EASILY AND CONSIDERED IT USEFUL FOR COMPLETING TASKS.

SUGGESTIONS:

>ADD A BUTTON TO AUTOMATICALLY SCROLL TO THE EXPLORATION SECTION FROM THE HOMEPAGE.
 >ALLOW SELECTION AND ISOLATION OF SPECIFIC CLUSTERS IN THE GLOBE OR PROVIDE A STATIC VIEW TO SEARCH FOR SPECIFIC IMAGES.
 >ENABLE CLOSING IMAGE CARDS BY CLICKING OUTSIDE THE CARD FOR SMOOTHER EXPLORATION.
 >CLARIFY HOW USERS CAN CONTRIBUTE TO THE DATASET, INCLUDING UPLOADING CONTENT.
 >ENSURE THE ACTIVE SECTION SELECTION REMAINS CONSISTENT DURING NAVIGATION.

ALESSIA

NAVIGATION AND FILTERS:

> STRUGGLED TO LOCATE THE "PEOPLE" SECTION.
 > EXPECTED FILTERS TO CLOSE AUTOMATICALLY WHEN CLICKING OUTSIDE THEIR WINDOW.
 >PREFERS TO FIND THE "CONTENT" FILTER BEFORE THE "STYLE" FILTER.
 > WHEN SELECTING MULTIPLE FILTERS (E.G., "BOY" + "GIRL"), EXPECTED BOTH TO APPLY TOGETHER.
 > FILTERS DO NOT CLOSE PROPERLY, AND FILTERED IMAGES DO NOT MATCH EXPECTATIONS.
 > TOOK TIME TO UNDERSTAND THE NAVIGATION LOGIC DUE TO THE PRECISION OF FILTERS.

INTERFACE AND USABILITY:

> SUGGESTED ADDING AN OPTION TO COPY IMAGES.
 > RECOMMENDS AN INITIAL ANIMATION TO GUIDE USERS, AS NAVIGATION SECTIONS AND PARALLAX EFFECTS ARE UNCOMMON.
 > SUGGESTS SIMPLIFYING THE PRIORITIZATION OF INFORMATION, ESPECIALLY FOR THE FILTERS.
 > NOTICED INCONSISTENCIES IN ICONS, POSSIBLY RELATED TO CODING ISSUES.

POSSIBLE IMPROVEMENTS

1. FILTER OPTIMIZATION:

- > ENABLE FILTERS TO CLOSE AUTOMATICALLY WHEN CLICKING OUTSIDE THEIR WINDOW.
- > REORGANIZE FILTERS TO DISPLAY “CONTENT” BEFORE “STYLE.”
- > ADD A SINGLE BUTTON TO REMOVE ALL ACTIVE FILTERS.

2. NAVIGATION AND USER INTERFACE:

- > INTRODUCE AN INITIAL ANIMATION TO GUIDE USERS IN NAVIGATING SECTIONS AND UNDERSTANDING THE PARALLAX DESIGN.
- > PROVIDE AN ALTERNATIVE STATIC VIEW LIKE THE GRID.

3. IMAGE MANAGEMENT:

- > IMPLEMENT A FEATURE TO COPY IMAGES DIRECTLY FROM THE SITE.
- > CREATE A USER PROFILE SECTION TO SAVE AND ACCESS FAVOURITE IMAGES.
- > ALLOW IMAGE CARDS TO CLOSE BY CLICKING OUTSIDE THE CARD FOR SMOOTHER EXPLORATION.
- > FIX UNPREDICTABLE BEHAVIOR WHEN CLICKING ON IMAGES.

4. SECTIONS AND CONTENT:

- > ENHANCE THE EDUCATION PAGE WITH MULTIMEDIA CONTENT BEYOND TEXT.

5. VISUALIZATION AND USABILITY:

- > IMPROVE THE VISIBILITY OF THE LEGEND IN THE “GLITCH” SECTION AND CLARIFY THE AXIS INTERPRETATION.
- > ALLOW USERS TO SELECT AND ISOLATE SPECIFIC CLUSTERS IN THE “SIMILARITY” GLOBE OR PROVIDE A STATIC ALTERNATIVE VIEW.
- > ENSURE FILTERS REMAIN ACTIVE WHEN SWITCHING BETWEEN “SIMILARITY” AND “OVERVIEW” VIEWS.

Applied improvements
and future improvements

B.5.1

Applied improvements

To enhance the interface experience, several improvements identified during user testing have been implemented, including:

> **Closing Filters and Image Cards:**

Filters and image cards can now be closed by clicking outside their respective windows, improving navigation and reducing friction.

> **Profile Page Development:**

The previously non-functional profile page on the navigation bar has been developed and is now fully operational, allowing users to access saved content seamlessly.

> **Improved Visualization Switcher Visibility:**

A blinking effect has been added to the visualization switcher buttons on the explore page, making them more noticeable and helping users understand that the visualization mode can be changed.

> **Tooltips for 3D Environment Exploration:**

A tooltip has been introduced to inform users that the interface is a 3D environment, guiding them in navigating and exploring the space more effectively.

Further Improvements

To enhance functionality, usability, and sustainability, the following updates are planned:

> **Image Upload:**

Add a feature to upload images, fostering collaboration and expanding the collection.

> **Improved Filters:**

Refine filtering options for more precise and efficient content discovery.

> **Content Collection:**

Enable users to add content directly to the personal collection.

> **Bug Fixes:**

Resolve issues with invisible but selectable images for a smoother user experience.

> **Education Page:**

Enrich the educational section with more interactive and engaging elements.

> **Energy Optimization:**

Implement improvements to reduce energy consumption and enhance sustainability.

These updates will improve functionality, ensure a seamless user experience, and align with the platform's sustainability goals.

C.

CITATIONS

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[FIG.3] Graphic ri-elaboration from: Generative AI Power Demand (Base Case). (2024, June 20). [CHART] Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bethkindig/2024/06/20/ai-power-consumption-rapidly-becoming-mission-critical/>

[FIG.4] Graphic ri-elaboration from: People Are Creating an Average of 34 Million Images Per Day. Statistics for 2024 (2023, August 15). [CHART] <https://journal.everypixel.com/ai-image-statistics>

[FIG.5] Graphic ri-elaboration from: People Are Creating an Average of 34 Million Images Per Day. Statistics for 2024 (2023, August 15). [CHART] <https://journal.everypixel.com/ai-image-statistics>

[FIG.6] Graphic scheme of research methodology (Alice Mioni - SLOMO: Reframing generative waste in the creative process (2025))

[FIG.7] Crawford, K., & Joler, V. (2018). Anatomy of an AI System [Review of Anatomy of an AI System]. <https://anatomyof.ai/>

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[FIG.9] Graphic scheme of mapping GenAI consumption (Alice Mioni - SLOMO: Reframing generative waste in the creative process (2025))

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[FIG.274] Graphic scheme of project touch-points (Alice Mioni - SLOMO: Reframing generative waste in the creative process (2025))

[FIG.275] Graphic ri-elaboration from: Knights, C. (2022, September 27). Low Carbon Digital Colour Palettes. Consider Digital Agency. <https://consider.digital/low-carbon-web-colour-palettes/>

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